

High Performance Bio-based Functional Coatings for Wood and Decorative Applications

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- OTHER**

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- CO** Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement
- CI** Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 1001/844/EC

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Executive summary

Biobased coatings are desired as part of the transition to a sustainable society, but have so far been difficult to develop, due to low performance compared with the prevailing specifications and high CO₂ footprints. PERFECOAT aims to develop and validate new coatings with significantly more than 25% bio-based components that meet and even surpass the current standards in three markets: 1) high-volume ultraviolet (UV)-curable clearcoats, 2) do-it-yourself (DIY) waterborne trim paints, and 3) DIY waterborne wall paints. Assessment of the environmental, techno-economic, and social impacts of the novel biobased products is an integral part of the project.

This document presents the assessment of social acceptance and potential social impacts, based on the stakeholder and impact categories applied in social life-cycle assessment (S-LCA). The study started with a baseline study in the initial project phase, followed by an interview study on the social acceptance of advanced biobased coatings, and finally a social impact assessment of the final formulations for UV-curable topcoats, where the project has achieved some of the most promising results.

The social acceptance study shows that the socio-political acceptance of bio-based coatings is high, given the societal goals of decarbonisation and transition towards a more circular economy. In recent years, the EU has implemented many conducive policies, and The Transition Pathway for the EU Chemicals Industry, launched in 2023, indicates a growing commitment also in the industry. In terms of market acceptance, there is increasing interest in biobased solutions, although high costs remain a challenge and the willingness to risk is influenced by geopolitical uncertainties. Concerning community acceptance, lack of knowledge and awareness is a problem. Willingness to pay is still limited, but there is a growing interest in some segments.

The assessment of potential social impacts shows that the two novel biobased formulations for UV-curable topcoats are likely to have positive impacts for most of the selected indicators. However, the difference between the novel alternatives and the conventional topcoat formulation considered for comparison is modest since several components and suppliers remain the same across the three alternatives.

In a shorter-term perspective, health and safety of workers is an area of uncertainty, where it is important to provide good documentation and apply common standards ensuring that

the bio-based innovations will enhance sustainability. For the wider society, the main area of risk is potential conflicts over land use, linked to conservation of biodiversity and food security, as the global demand for biomass eventually may exceed its availability. Here, one of the novel, biobased formulations scores higher than the other, as the novel ingredient in this alternative is based on residues from forestry and wood processing, whereas the other is based on poplar and contains other components with bio-based content without a specified source.

Transparency has been a challenge in the complex, global value chains of the coating industry, and given their early stage of development, the novel bio-based formulations in PERFECOAT currently score lower on this than the conventional alternative. However, they may have a positive impact over time, as they face comprehensive documentation requirements, and sustainability will be among their main attractive features. Consumers will benefit from a wider set of consumers' choices, and enhanced sense of wellbeing from buying and having products that help preserve natural resources for future generations.

For local communities, green value creation and employment effects are foreseen. For the value chain actors, benefits in terms of knowledge development, green competitive advantage and opportunities for sustainable product expansion are also anticipated. It must be emphasized, however, that the focal solutions are at an early stage of development. Their contribution to sustainability transition will depend on the source of feedstock, as well as the achieved functionality, environmental impacts, and acceptance among key stakeholders, within a changing societal context. This underscores the complexity of social impacts, and the need to consider this dimension as an integral part in technological innovation processes.

1 Introduction

PERFECOAT aims to develop and validate new industrial wood coatings and decorative coatings with significantly more than 25% bio-based components that surpass the current quality and sustainability standards for 1) high-volume ultraviolet (UV)-curable clearcoats, 2) do-it-yourself (DIY) waterborne trim paints, and 3) DIY waterborne wall paints. An integral part of the project is the application of life-cycle methodologies to assess environmental, techno-economic and social impacts of bio-based products. This document presents the assessment of social acceptance and potential social impacts of the novel bio-based coatings.

Social acceptance holds a central place in the assessment, since market, socio-political and consumer acceptance is a precondition for the uptake of novel products. Social acceptance is addressed with basis in a desk study and set of stakeholder interviews that were carried out before the final formulations in PERFECOAT were selected. Thus, the part on social acceptance relates to advanced bio-based architectural coatings and coating components more broadly, and not to a specific formulation.

The social impact assessment (SIA) is focused on the final formulations selected for UV-curable topcoats, as per September 2024. These were selected based on the impression that this so far is the application with the most promising results, in terms of functionality and potential for upscaling. The novel solutions are compared with a conventional topcoat formulation, and the potential social impacts are assessed in a multi-criteria framework, drawing on the stakeholder groups and main impact categories emphasized in S-LCA (UNEP 2009, 2020). Due to limited availability of data, it has not been possible to provide a very detailed analysis. The assessment is based on information from the stakeholder interviews, a survey among the project partners, and review of the annual financial statements and sustainability reports of key actors in the market for the respective components, plus relevant research and grey literature.

When it comes to social acceptance, there is clearly a positive trend. The socio-political acceptance of bio-based coatings is high, given the societal goals of decarbonisation and transition towards a more circular economy. In terms of market acceptance, there is increasing interest in biobased solutions, although high costs remain a challenge and the willingness to risk is influenced by geopolitical uncertainties. Concerning community

acceptance, lack of knowledge and awareness is a challenge. Willingness to pay is still limited, but there is growing interest in some segments.

Considering social impacts, the main area of risk in a long-term perspective is potential conflicts over land use, linked to conservation of biodiversity and food security, as the global demand for biomass eventually may exceed its availability. In a shorter-term perspective, human rights, fair wages, and the health and safety of workers are areas of uncertainty, where it is important to provide good documentation and apply common standards ensuring that the biobased innovations will enhance sustainable development. Transparency has been a challenge in the complex, global value chains of the coating industry, and given their early stage of development, the novel biobased formulations in PERFECOAT currently score lower on this than the conventional alternative. However, they may have a positive impact over time, given that they are associated with detailed documentation requirements, and sustainability will be among their main selling points.

Consumers will benefit from a wider set of consumers' choices, and enhanced sense of wellbeing, from applying products that help preserve natural resources for future generations. Enhanced utilisation of waste, with local value creation and employment effects, are other social impacts that can be expected. For the value chain actors, benefits in terms of knowledge development, green competitive advantage, and scaling impacts stimulating the development and uptake of other biobased products are also anticipated. It must be emphasized, however, that the focal solutions are at an early stage of development. Their contribution to sustainability transition will depend on the achieved functionality, environmental impacts, and acceptance among key stakeholders, as well as the changing societal context. This underscores the complexity of social impacts, and the need to consider this dimension as an integral part in technological innovation processes.

The report is structured as follows: Chapter 2 specifies the objective of the deliverable. Chapter 3, subsequently, provides a brief background, on the key concepts and perspectives applied. In chapter 4, we describe the main steps in our methodology. The findings from the study on social acceptance are discussed in chapter 5, and chapter 6 presents the main findings from the SIA, structured according to the relevant stakeholder- and impact categories. In chapter 7, we provide an overall assessment of potential social impacts, bringing together the results for the various selected impact categories, for the novel biobased formulations as well as the conventional, largely fossil-based baseline formulation. Chapter 8, finally, is a summary conclusion.

2 Objective

The objectives of this study are: 1) to illuminate the social acceptance of novel biobased coating solutions; 2) to assess the potential social impacts of such solutions (and compare them with the fossil counterpart).

Social acceptance is emphasized because it is a precondition for the uptake of novel solutions. Our aim in this regard is to assess the current level of acceptance, as perceived by some of the relevant stakeholders, and to identify some of the main factors hindering and contributing to the social acceptance of novel, biobased coatings for the markets targeted in PERFECOAT.

Social impact assessment (SIA) can be defined as "the process of identifying the future consequences of a current or proposed action(s), which are related to individuals, organizations and social macro-systems" (Becker 2001). In our case, where the focus is on biobased technologies in an early stage of development, the study can be classified as a strategic assessment, aiming is to shed light on potential benefits to society and thus promote the new solutions as elements in sustainability transition, while also drawing attention to potentially adverse impacts (Partidário 2015, 2016). To this end, we apply the stakeholder categories and main impact categories defined in social life cycle assessment (S-LCA). We consider potential social impacts both for the relevant value chain actors, workers, local communities, consumers, and the wider society.

The focal solutions are the two final formulations PERFECOAT has developed for UV-curable top coatings for furniture, in comparison with a conventional alternative. At the current stage, it is not possible to be very specific about social impacts, but it is indeed important to identify potential benefits and risk areas, so-called "social hotspots", which must be considered from an early stage. Thus, our aim is to provide a systematic assessment to identify such areas, which should be examined in more detail as and when more data becomes available.

3 Background and key concepts

Increasing focus on the social dimension of sustainability is underpinned by the political developments at the European level. The European Green Deal aims to facilitate achievement of the climate targets and reduction of CO₂ emissions, contribute to preservation of natural resources, as well as create jobs necessary to enable a just transition towards a sustainable society. The Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (2023) and the proposed EU Social Taxonomy are two instruments pushing social sustainability higher on the agenda. Several frameworks and approaches are applicable to address social dimensions of sustainability, e.g., social life cycle assessment (UNEP-SETAC, 2009; UNEP, 2020). Social acceptance, i.e., desirability of products and solutions at stake by different stakeholder groups, is an important prerequisite the uptake of novel innovation and their potential contributions to sustainability, as no impact can occur if the solutions are not desired and accepted and consequently might be hindered in their implementation. Social acceptance and social impacts, therefore, are two key concepts in this deliverable.

3.1 Social acceptance

Social acceptance is sometimes conflated to only public acceptance, and often restricted to describing the positions taken by certain actors, often 'the public', in response to actions and initiatives taken by others. However, the conceptualisation of social acceptance in sustainability transition studies stresses that social acceptance must be understood as a set of activities unfolding over time in complex, multilayered processes, influencing the development, uptake, and potential impacts of innovations (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007; Wolsink, 2018). Seeing it as a process phenomenon, three principal dimensions of social acceptance can be distinguished: community, market, and socio-political acceptance (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007). The three dimensions are important to address the process dynamics, where for example socio-political acceptance may be ahead of market acceptance, or vice versa, and/or depend on different aspects of the focal innovation. Social acceptance relates to the necessary conditions for innovation processes, the conditions needed for implementation, and the consequences of such implementation, as well as the specific technology or product considered (Wolsink, 2018). Thus, there is a close link between social impacts and social acceptance. Addressing the three dimensions of social acceptance also allows to incorporate views of several stakeholder categories and, therefore, this definition is one of the key ones followed in this report.

According to Wüstenhagen et al. (2007), socio-political acceptance reflects the interest and will of key stakeholders and policy actors to promote the solutions and implement effective enabling policies. Their willingness to promote and support these solutions enables creation of effective institutions necessary to foster and enhance market and community acceptance (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007). Community acceptance reflects to what extent an innovation is desired by the relevant communities, including e.g., local authorities, residents, and end users. Community acceptance can change over time, usually showing higher levels of acceptance at the beginning of the process, then decreasing and reaching (relatively) low acceptance, followed by a higher level of acceptance after the implementation of the project is started or even complete. Community acceptance is often closely linked with the social impacts an initiative creates or may create, for example, in form of costs and benefits and their distribution, and involvement in the decision-making processes or lack of such involvement (Gross, 2007). The last dimension, market acceptance, covers attitudes and behaviour of users/consumers, investors, and intra-firm acceptance (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007).

Figure 1: The triangle of social acceptance (adopted from Wüstenhagen et al., 2007).

To provide a nuanced understanding of the social acceptance of advanced biobased coating solutions, even if they still are at an early development stage, we also draw upon psychological perspectives on social acceptance (e.g., Huijts et al. 2012). Huijts et al. (2012) suggests that acceptance of a technology depends strongly on the individual choices made by actors. These depend on values and goals, as well as rational evaluation

of the costs, risks, and benefits of alternative options. Thus, technology acceptance is also influenced by moral evaluations (i.e., perception of what is the most appropriate in a particular situation when normative goals are at stake), and what “feels best”, even among rational business actors (ibid.). Combining these perspectives allows us to consider, among other, current user practices, knowledge development processes and current gaps, drivers, and barriers for the adoption of biobased coating solutions, as well as broader reflections on the role of biobased coating solutions in sustainability transition.

3.2 Social impacts and sustainability

While it is necessary to include three pillars (economic, environmental, and social sustainability) for assessing sustainability of products and solutions, for example, through the life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA) framework (Zamagni, 2012), the social 'pillar' of sustainability is vaguely defined, and there is no consensus on what adequate criteria for social sustainability are (Murphy, 2012). Social impact assessment (SIA) provides a holistic view of all intended and unintended social consequences, both positive and negative, of a product or planned intervention. The concept is partly overlapping, and often used interchangeably with social sustainability assessment, since social sustainability can be related to maximum positive and minimum negative social impacts. Equity, awareness for sustainability, participation, and social cohesion (Murphy, 2012), and basic needs and quality of life, social justice, and social coherence (Littig and Griessler, 2005) have previously been identified as core dimensions of social sustainability.

S-LCA, which increasingly is applied, differs from SIA in that it aims to address the whole life cycle of the focal solution (UNEP-SETAC, 2009). Key dimensions or impact categories addressed are human rights, working conditions, health and safety, cultural heritage, governance, and socio-economic repercussions. While S-LCA provides a comprehensive framework, it has been argued that it lacks the required empirical evidence to validate it as an effective measure of the social performance of a bio-based product (Falcone & Imbert, 2018). Besides, a full S-LCA requires large amounts of data, which cannot easily be found for products that still are in early stages of development, and it is generally time- and resource-consuming.

Among an increasing number of S-LCA studies focused on bio-based products (Macombe et al., 2013; Rafiaani et al., 2018; Siebert et al., 2018a), several (e.g. Ekener-Petersen et al. 2014; Matos & Silvestre, 2013; Siebert et al., 2018b) recommend a stakeholder

participatory approach to develop measures to enhance social sustainability. Falcone et al. (2019) argue that such an approach also is needed to specify assessment criteria and indicators for bio-based products that encompass the viewpoints of the relevant interest groups. They provide a two-step methodological framework encompassing (a) identification of the relevant social impact categories, subcategories, and indicators and (b) validation of these factors, according to participatory stakeholder involvement. Applying this framework enables consideration of a restricted number of social indicators, reducing the amount of data needed for assessing and decreasing related costs (Falcone et al., 2019) and making it therefore suitable for assessment of novel solutions in early stage of development anchored in complex value chains with limited data availability. The SIA in PERFECOAT applied this approach and paid special attention to social acceptance as a factor influencing the sustainability, market, and transition potential of new bio-based coatings.

4 Methods and materials

4.1 Baseline study

To gain an initial overview of the value chain and prevailing perspectives on the impacts and possible transition pathways for the coatings industry, a baseline study was conducted. It included desk study of relevant websites and grey literature, as well as a state-of-the-art review of research literature on social impacts and social sustainability assessment of bio-based products. The literature review was conducted in January 2022. The identified articles covered sustainability assessments, social sustainability assessments, social lifecycle assessments of biobased products in general, as earlier search for similar analyses and assessments of biobased coatings has demonstrated a knowledge gap in this regard.

The literature review showed that only few studies have addressed the topics of social impacts and acceptance of bio-based products. Among these, several (e.g., Macombe et al., 2013; Ekener-Petersen et al., 2014; Falcone et al., 2018; Siebert et al., 2018a) apply the S-LCA as framework. However, the reviewed literature also points out the need to pre-select relevant impact categories adjusted to a specific solution and case context (Falcone et al., 2019; Rafiaani et al., 2019; Siebert et al., 2018b). Most of the reviewed studies also consider expert and/or stakeholder involvement as a necessary part of the assessment, either through a survey, interviews, workshop discussion(s) or a combination of these methods. In line with these recommendations and to try and get as much data as possible, considering that the focal solutions are in an early stage of development, we combined these data collection methods.

4.2 Data sources

Stakeholder interviews represent an important data source for this assessment. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with representatives of different stakeholders, both within and outside the value chain. These were conducted online, in most cases by two researchers, and detailed notes were taken. The interview questions were based on the key theoretical concepts described above (Chapter 3). Thus, they covered factors influencing social acceptance of the novel biobased coating solutions, while also addressing the stakeholders' perspectives and activities concerning social sustainability, and what they saw as potential social impact categories.

The baseline study identified several external stakeholders it would be relevant to consult, but it was difficult to get responses from these. Therefore, we included some of the industry

partners of the PERFECOAT project. Besides data collection, the interviews with the project partners were used to test and adjust the initial interview guide, as well as identify relevant external stakeholders (snowballing method). Overall, thirteen interviews were conducted, within the period October 2022-July 2024. Table 1 an overview of the interviews and stakeholder categories covered.

Table 1: Overview of interviewed stakeholders.

Stakeholder category	Number
End-user	1
Paint producer	5
Supplier of (biobased) components	4
Sector organisations	2
Public authority	1
Total	13

Data from the stakeholder interviews were also used in the assessment of potential social impacts. Although the final formulations were not yet selected when the interviews took place, the interviewees provided relevant information and reflections on some of the aspects considered in the SIA. The interview data was analysed using thematic analysis.

For the SIA, we conducted a systematic review of the annual reports, sustainability reports, and Codes of Conduct available for key actors supplying the various components in the relevant coating formulations. For some components, identified with a specific name and product registration number, we referred to the specific supplier, and for others, which rather represent a type or category of chemicals, we included the documents of 5-7 suppliers identified as central by relevant market analysts. Further, other data sources were used for triangulation. These sources include company webpages, reports, government documents and strategies. Due to limited availability of data, we also include references to previous research in our assessment, for some of the considered impact categories.

In addition, participant observation in the workshops and project meetings (both internal and external meetings) was crucial as a data collection method, given the development stage of the solutions in focus and limited availability of data.

4.3 Assessment framework

The methodology selected for the social impact assessment is anchored in S-LCA, as one of the most established approaches for sustainability assessment of products. We followed the approach suggested by Falcone et al. (2019), to cover the main impact categories and stakeholder groups identified as crucial, but select the subcategories and indicators deemed most relevant for the studied case, in dialogue with relevant stakeholders, in this case consisting of the project partners in PERFE COAT, which represent the whole value chain for biobased coatings.

Selection of relevant criteria and indicators

Based on the above-mentioned literature review, a preliminary set of impact categories and sub-categories was identified. Thereafter, at a physical consortium meeting held 26-28 April, 2022 a workshop was conducted to validate the identified impact categories and discuss relevant indicators for the respective impact categories. The participants were representatives of all project partners, thus including perspectives from all parts of the value chain, as well as a group of researchers with different disciplinary backgrounds, ranging from chemistry, biochemistry, health and safety, to industrial economics and social science. The participants were asked to rank the preliminary set of impact categories and sub-categories in terms of relevance, and also given opportunity to propose other subcategories or indicators.

The results from the groupwork were collected and systematized in a list of impact categories identified for the present study. This list together with other sources was also used as basis for questions in the interviews with the relevant stakeholders. Following the interviews, the list was complemented with additional impact categories, resulting in a final list of impact categories, which were applied in this study (Table 2).

Table 2: Stakeholder categories and impact categories considered in this SIA.

Stakeholder categories	Impact categories
Value chain actors	Knowledge development
	Fair competition
	Sustainable product expansion
	Green competitive advantage
	Acceptance
Workers	Human rights

	Fair wages
	Equal opportunities
	Health and safety
Local communities	Value creation
	Support for community development
Consumers	Acceptance
	Health and safety
	Transparency
	Wellbeing (satisfaction from using more sustainable products)
Wider society	Food security
	Land use
	Substitution
	(Circularity) Making use of waste
	Acceptance

Following Falcone et al. (2019), who aimed to identify the most relevant social impact categories and indicators for bio-based products, we include some of the key impact categories highlighted in S-LCA (UNEP, 2009; UNEP, 2020), namely health and safety, labour rights and decent work, and human rights. We also consider social acceptability as a crucial dimension but have chosen not to consider cultural heritage or migration, which were not considered very relevant by Falcone et al. (2019), nor by the consulted stakeholders in our case.

Unlike Falcone et al. (2019), who did not find social benefits and community engagement relevant, we consider these aspects as important. Ideally, we would relate this to alignment and support for local/regional development strategies but considering the scope and limited availability of data in our case, we define the related impact category as “support for community development”. Moreover, freedom of association and collective bargaining is referenced in several human rights instruments. Falcone et al. (2019) therefore argue that these aspects can be taken for granted. However, many of our stakeholders considered these as important, and e.g., the right to collective bargaining is highlighted in the sustainability reporting of many of the key actors in the European coating industry. We therefore include these aspects, via the category “fair wages”. Child labour is not included in our framework, as compliance with the relevant laws and regulations can be considered as a necessary requirement, and therefore not an impact or dimension of social sustainability as such.

In line with some of the overarching perspectives on social sustainability mentioned above (Murphy, 2012; Littig and Griessler, 2005), which include wellbeing as an aspect under quality of life, we include consumer wellbeing, as satisfaction from buying and applying more environment friendly products, i.e. linked to bequest value and preservation of resources for future generations, is one area where novel, biobased products are likely to have an impact. With a view to sustainability transition, we also reason that impacts related to innovation capacity, opportunity for development of additional, biobased products that may substitute for less sustainable alternatives, and contribution towards the wider societal aims of enhancing circularity and substituting fossil-based materials with renewable alternatives, must be considered in a framework for social sustainability assessment of biobased products.

The specific indicators applied for each impact category were tailored at a later stage in the assessment, based on the level of detail with which the novel, biobased coating solutions were described, and the types of data available. In line with the recommendations in the relevant research literature, we include both quantitative and qualitative indicators. All are assessed applying an ordinal ranking system (1-3), where 1 refers to the least positive impact, 2 to a medium-level impact, and 3 to the strongest positive (or least negative) impact.

Preliminary results were presented at an online workshop with the project partners, 20th September 2024. Ideally, a validation workshop with a wider set of stakeholders should have been included, but due to time constraints in the final project phase, this was not possible.

5 Social acceptance study

Social acceptance is an important prerequisite for the solutions to have any social impact, as rather limited or no impact can occur if the solutions are not desired and accepted. The social acceptance study provides insights into factors influencing the desirability of the novel biobased coating solutions at stake by broader stakeholder groups. In this chapter, we present and discuss the findings from the study, according to the three dimensions highlighted in previous research.

5.1 Market acceptance

According to Markets and Markets, the bio-based coatings market was valued at EUR 10.5 billion in 2022, and projected to grow at a CAGR of 9.5 % to reach EUR 16.6 billion in 2027.¹ Still, manufacturers are reporting a weak demand, with key actors estimating the bio-based coatings market share to be less than 10 %. In the resins industry, the bio-based proportion could be even lower, in the range of 5 %, albeit with further growth anticipated for the coming years. While awareness of the climate crisis is increasing, the readiness to take a risk is low particularly in the times of economic and political uncertainties we have now.²

Gaining market acceptance is important for the novel solutions, and stakeholders point out increasing focus on sustainability among investors as one of the drivers for the work with biobased coating solutions. At the same time, increasing focus needs to be supported by willingness to pay, that currently remains low. Green UV-curable coatings are usually more expensive compared to others, but increasingly popular, especially in Europe and North America, where they are brought forward by environment regulations and norms. In the Asia Pacific and Middle East the market is seen as more challenging, due to less awareness and compliance with emission standards.³

International market analysts point to several factors behind the remaining high prices. A main reason is high initial investment, as the UV curing equipment and technology is costly, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises. Moreover, UV-cured coatings may not adhere well to all substrates, and ensuring compatibility with a wide range of materials remains a challenge. In applications with complex shapes or thick coatings, UV light may

¹Bio-based Coatings Market | 2022 - 2027 | MarketsandMarkets

² Bio-based coating: Despite challenges, optimism prevails - News and insights for the European coatings industry (european-coatings.com)

³ <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/uv-coatings-market-92686798.html>

have limited penetration, affecting the curing process, and certain chemicals used in UV-cured coatings can pose health risks if not properly managed. UV-cured coatings may face limitations in terms of flexibility and impact resistance compared to some traditional coatings.⁴

Some of the interviewees also emphasized that the market interest may differ across regions. The interest level in Europe is currently high, due to conducive regulations, but the willingness to pay is rather low. In other regions, e.g. the Middle East, the willingness to pay may be higher for some products, if they are framed e.g., as "luxury products". Customers in Northern Europe expect environmental benefits to be granted, implying that higher prices are not accepted. One big customer emphasised their willingness to support suppliers who work towards more biobased content and deliver more environmentally friendly solutions, and the driving role of this big player was also mentioned by several other interviewees. At the same time, it was made clear that this support shall not take a form of "green premium".

According to the perspectives noted above (e.g., Wolsink, 2018; Huijts et al., 2012), the perceived social benefits and values associated with the solutions in focus can also influence their market acceptance. The stakeholder interviews revealed that expected benefits relate to the sustainability transition potential of the solutions at stake, namely, the need to work in the direction of green transition and development of environmentally friendly solutions. These perspectives, however, are nuanced by their requirement to document the environmental benefits. In this regard, stakeholders point at the lack of harmonised requirements behind environmental labels and marks. A big number of these labels and marks combined with limited knowledge on the consumers' side could make communicating of the benefits of the coatings challenging.

While the benefits can be present, the stakeholders set clear requirements on the functionalities of the new products that must be as good as the conventional ones. At the same time, given the novelty of the solutions and differing level of knowledge among the industry actors in this regard, the stakeholders' views differ with regard to the functionalities that considered to be crucial. The identified functionalities in stakeholders' focus include, e.g., colour, water and fire resistance, colour fading, smell. They also differentiate between the application areas of the coatings suggesting that there might be

⁴ <https://www.verifiedmarketresearch.com/product/uv-cured-coatings-market/>

differences in which functionalities are more valued depending on this. Further, they point out other aspects that might influence the acceptance of these new solutions by the users, e.g., their influence on indoor air quality.

Compatibility with existing infrastructures, equipment and routines is another factor influencing the market acceptance of the existing solutions, reinforcing the points behind high prices (mentioned above). Stakeholders point out that lack of this compatibility will require value chain actors to invest in new equipment and reorganisation of existing processes and routines that might be costly and resource demanding. Last, but not least, the market acceptance of the novel biobased solutions can be influenced by the seasonality of the biomass used in production. Availability of the biomass of necessary quality biomass can, therefore, represent a challenge for the upscaling of the focal solutions and hinder their market acceptance. The type of biomass becomes crucial in this regard.

Overall, the market acceptance of the biobased coating solutions is rather emerging and depends on several factors. Based on the interviews with selected stakeholders, to facilitate and increase the market acceptance ensuring and documenting the functionalities, as well as the compatibility of the solutions with the existing infrastructures is key. While the willingness to pay remains low, it is necessary to address other aspects that can influence market acceptance of the novel biobased solutions where possible.

5.2 Community acceptance

So far, little is known about consumer perceptions and reactions regarding bio-based production processes and specific bio-based consumer products (Sijtsema et al., 2016). However, some of the studies conducted indicate that even if they are not very familiar with such products, respondents indicate a strong interest in buying them when they are comparable to non-bio-based alternatives in terms of price and benefits (ibid.). According to one of the key actors, the concept of 'bio-based' or 'biorenewable' can easier be explained to today's consumer and have greater emotional impact than 'sustainable', and there has been a substantial increase in enquiries for such products.

On the other hand, recent research shows that many consumers lack awareness of the existence of bio-based products, related knowledge is low, and labels and brands are often unknown (Ruf et al., 2022). Additionally, some consumers have wrong assumptions about the environmental impact of bio-based materials. Consumer preferences vary between product groups, but often factors like price or functionality are more important than bio-

based materials. Sijtsema et al. (2016) further note that negative associations related to distrust, e.g., where production processes are located in China, can be of influence. Having a coherent product concept is also important, as consumers dislike inconsistencies, e.g., they tend to expect that a biobased product should perform better in terms of health and safety, and fair trade, as well environment-friendliness (ibid.).

As the biobased coatings in focus in this study are at an early stage of development and not linked to a specific production site, we do not have any interviews with stakeholders representing communities where local impacts from novel biobased coatings can be observed. However, the interviews and interactions with other stakeholders reveal several factors that can influence community acceptance of the solutions at stake and demonstrate that they recognise the importance of the origin of biomass and the need to source biomass that has been produced sustainably. At the same time, there are big differences in what they perceive as sustainable biomass.

Community acceptance can depend a lot on how citizens living near to the location of the implementation and use of the technology perceive the effects of this technology implementation and use on them. This is especially relevant when decisions are made by others, as it relates to procedural and distributive justice are perceived (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007). Our findings show that factors potentially influencing community acceptance can take place on the side where the input for the technology or solution is produced and sourced, i.e. biomass. The interviewed stakeholders point out several concerns regarding the origin of biomass. For example, the biomass needs to be sustainably produced, meaning, among other, that it should not compete with food production. At the same time, interviewed actors expect that their supply management routines and compliance with the required regulatory frameworks are well-established and functioning to ensure that needed biomass is produced sustainably. Several interviewed actors consider local value chains as an enabler of higher transparency of the value chains, although not all the actors have immediate plans in this regard.

Community acceptance can also relate to labour and human rights of workers involved in production and collection of the biomass. In this regard, the informants, however, believe that aspects of labour and human rights do not present a risk for them, as they only operate in Europe where these issues must be addressed adequately. Similarly, aspects of health and safety of workers during several phases could influence community acceptance if serious incidents would take place. Nevertheless, none of the interviewed stakeholders

raised concerns in this regard, as most of them expect the new solutions (and respective steps in their production) to comply with the necessary laws, regulations and established organisational routines.

5.3 Socio-political acceptance

Socio-political acceptance, as mentioned earlier (Chapter 4.1), relates to the presence of supportive policies and regulations that can facilitate the uptake of novel technologies and solutions (Wüstenhagen et al., 2007). With regard to the presence of overarching policies and regulations, the informants report that these are in place. These include, e.g., European Green Deal (2019) that demonstrates continuously increasing sustainability focus in Europe. In addition to the environmental sustainability, the European Green Deal also aims to support impacted regions, industries, workers, households and consumers. The chemical industry declares itself to be a part of the European Green Deal with an ambition to contribute to the EU's decarbonisation goals (EC, 2023).

The development of novel biobased solutions is aligned with some of the objectives of the EU Bioeconomy strategy (EC, 2018), such as sustainable management of natural resources, reducing dependence on non-renewable resources, as well as strengthening European competitiveness and create jobs. Further, the increasing focus on sustainability and transition to a renewable bioeconomy is reflected in increasing requirements on sustainability reporting. EU Taxonomy, Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR) and Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) are three key regulatory instruments in the EU aimed at supporting sustainable activities, with CSRD being directly relevant for companies who need to disclose the impacts of their activities on social dimensions governance and sustainability.

The increasing focus on sustainability is also reflected in the actors' sustainability work and practices. We recognise differing focus among the informants with regard which aspects they emphasise in their sustainability work. For example, our informants report differing perceptions of sustainability in the industry, where biobased solutions can relate to sustainability, but other ways we work with sustainability, e.g. through recycling, are also part of the sustainability work. Further, the interviewed actors use different tools for documenting their sustainability work. The choice of these tools is sometimes related to the requirements on sustainability reporting that they receive from their customers. Among the most spread sustainability management tools is Eco Vadis. Eco Vadis is a platform that aims to help companies in addressing their sustainability work. Further, it provides a

service of sustainability rating, emphasising that this rating takes place within other actors who use Eco Vadis. This setup suggests that the results are relative and further sustainability improvements are possible.⁵ Eco Vadis requires its users to report on four main topics; environment, labour and human rights, ethics, and sustainable procurement. The system can be used both for own assessment, as well as the assessment of the value chain and suppliers. The actors usually do not know which dimensions and aspects their customers choose when conducting their assessments of their suppliers' sustainability work.

Eco Vadis is a recognised partner for Together for Sustainability, an initiative to promote sustainability that several big suppliers of the coating ingredients/components are part of. At the same time, other supply chain management tools are also present and are linked to local regulations on supply chain management, both national and regional/European. One example mentioned by the stakeholders in this regard is IntegrityNext, a platform that enables suppliers to address similar topics as EcoVadis (e.g., Labour and Human Rights, a number of topics related to Environment). While most of the mentioned tools and reporting routines include aspects relevant for the social dimension of sustainability, the interviewed stakeholders report lower interest in the social dimension of sustainability among their partners. Depending on the position in the value chain, actors must comply with different standards and set related requirements to their suppliers. For example, EPF standard was used by some actors, while it is outside of scope for others.

While overarching policies and directives related to sustainability are in place, and actors have started to work in this direction, creating a supportive environment for the novel solutions, it is necessary to address whether these are supported by other more specific instruments that could enable the necessary transition. With certain programmes and support mechanism being in place, several stakeholders have reported that the existing support mechanisms do not necessarily target this type of solutions. Several interviewed stakeholders have their own R&D departments and direct resources to support the work with biobased solutions. Participation in the EU projects is mentioned as another possibility to work in this direction. In addition, the interviewed stakeholders perceive that coating industry in general and separate customers (with few exceptions) as well lack specific targets with regard to biobased solutions. Lack of these targets that could be translated into specific requirements are pointed out as one barrier for higher socio-political acceptance. As mentioned earlier, few exceptions exist, and given the size of these actors

⁵ <https://ecovadis.com/>

their targets have indeed become an important driver for the work of the actors in the value chain on the biobased solutions.

Further, the interviewed stakeholders mentioned that their work on biobased solutions receives positive feedback, but also must comply with multiple mandatory norms and regulations. This compliance can influence both market acceptance and broader socio-political acceptance. While this aspect is non-discussable, proving and documenting the necessary qualities can become resource demanding. In addition, requirements by national regulatory authorities in different countries differ. For example, actors mention Denmark's Asthma and Allergy requirements as some of the strictest. Some of the most important sources of requirements mentioned are REACH regulation, standard for architectural paintings in Europe, ECHA rules, EU Painting Directive, and standards setting requirements for stability, wear-and-tear. Failing to meet the mandatory requirements will challenge the acceptance of the novel biobased solutions.

In addition to the mandatory requirements, novel solutions can consider obtaining environmental labels and marks. While the informants point them out as important, they also report the huge variety of these marks and labels, as well as differing requirements behind them. Further, the informants report that the level of knowledge among customers on the requirements and the meaning of these differing labels and marks is varying and often low. However, these environmental labels and marks set the requirements (although non-mandatory by definition) that can also influence market acceptance.

5.4 Chapter summary

Overall, the results demonstrate that the socio-political acceptance of the novel biobased coating solutions is high in terms of alignment with the broader socio-political goals and regulations. However, the interviews show that specific targets and requirements in the industry is lacking. This might have a positive impact on market acceptance, which is increasing but still limited by low willingness to pay and remaining questions regarding performance. Requirements from key customers (e.g., IKEA) remain one of the most important drivers and are likely to further increase market acceptance, however clearer targets and/or incentives could help accelerate the positive development.

Current developments of biobased solutions come with higher costs. Thus, facilitating and improving market acceptance of these solutions would require their improved price competitiveness. In addition, proven records of good performance are necessary to ensure higher market acceptance. For the latter, different users and markets emphasise importance of different features. These varying perceptions reflect the level of knowledge

among stakeholders, which for now remains low. Improved documentation and communication of the wider environmental and social benefits of novel biobased coatings could facilitate market acceptance further.

Regarding community acceptance there is limited pre-existing knowledge, and due to the early stage of development and limited overview of where the biomass would come from, it was also difficult to address this dimension in the present case. Nevertheless, community acceptance is a crucial dimension. For the focal solutions, community acceptance would not necessarily depend only on where the solutions are produced or taken in use, but also on where the feedstock will come from. Our interviews reveal that, e.g., jobs creation, human and labour rights, use of land and water related to the production can be crucial for community and end-user acceptance. While some of these aspects should be covered via existing regulations and sustainability reporting requirements, and sometimes are addressed through standards and ecolabelling, consumers' access to and knowledge of these labels and certifications is low. Increased transparency, on social as well as environmental sustainability, is necessary to ensure broader acceptance when/if upscaling is to take place.

6 Social impact assessment

6.1 Solutions in focus

For early-stage solutions, where technology development is still ongoing, it is difficult to decide when to draw the line and say this is the solution that will be assessed. Advantages of waiting as long as possible relate to the relevance of the assessment results. At the same time, the main disadvantage relates to time constraints. As the technology development is ongoing, partners naturally wish to keep the details confidential. Therefore, it is also challenging to provide definitions that are specific enough to relate to the developed technology in particular, yet broad and “concrete” enough for reference to be made to existing data sources, and for external stakeholders to be able to relate to the solutions and make sense of the assessment results.

In this case, we use the formulations for bio-based UV-curable top coatings provided by the project partners in September 2024. The shares of content are confidential, but the key components for the most promising alternatives are listed below (Table 3). In the Biobased Alternative A, the total biobased content is a bit lower than in Biobased Alternative B.

Table 3: Formulations for the focal, biobased solutions (September 2024).

Biobased Alternative A	Biobased alternative B
Novel, biobased binder (from xylose) GPTA Ebecryl 4690 Laromer PO77F Tego Airex 990 Jetfine 2 Acematt OK412 HF2086 Tego Rad 2500	Novel, biobased binder (from cellobiose) DPHA Laromer PO77F Tego Airex 990 Jetfine 2 Acematt OK412 HF2086 Tego Rad 2500

6.1.1 Key components in Alternative A

In alternative A, the novel bio-based binder is based on xylan, provided by a European innovator in biomass products. Xylan is a polysaccharide found in plants, and the third most abundant biopolymer on earth. In this case, it is produced from poplar grown in Ireland. The xylan is processed into xylose, which for simplicity can be described as wood sugar. The xylose is combined with fatty acid, which in this case also is bio-based, produced from wood residues.

Further, *Glyceryl Propoxy Triacrylate (GPTA)* is mainly used in wood paint, PVC paint, plastic paint, metal paint, offset printing ink, flexographic printing, screen printing, and varnish. GPTA is partly fossil-based, but can also be partly biobased, as the glycerol can be made from e.g., alcohol. It can be produced from plants (e.g., olives, soybeans, other). One of the key suppliers is Sigma-Aldrich, based in Switzerland. There are also a couple of other European producers, but by far the largest share of GPTA is produced in China.⁶

Ebecryl 4690 is presented by the producer as an energy-curable, Tin-free, urethane acrylate with ~27% bio-carbon offering long outdoor durability for clear and pigmented coats. It is solvent-free and presents a high reactivity for an effective productivity and brings high hardness after cure with strong substrate protection.⁷

6.1.2 Key components in alternative B

In alternative B, the novel, biobased component is based on cellobiose, based on wood residues from forestry (birchwood), and/or wood processing industry, based on raw material from local (European) certified and sustainably managed forests. The cellobiose is broken down into two cellulosic sugars (C5 (rich in xylose), and C6 (rich in glucose)). The producer is a private European company which is implementing a new cutting-edge technology to produce chemicals from wood residues.

Acrylated dipentaerythritol (DPHA) is a multifunctional reactive diluent that is useful in ultraviolet light (UV) and electron beam (EB) curable coatings where improved cure response, hardness and scratch/abrasion resistance are desired. DPHA is composed predominately of esters of dipentaerythritol.⁸ Dipentaerythritol, is produced via condensation of acetaldehyde with formaldehyde.⁹ Some of the relevant producers in

⁶ https://www.chemicalbook.com/ChemicalProductProperty_EN_CB0365121.htm

⁷ <https://allnex.com/en/product/1d90432e-f37d-450c-bb97-888369c06670/ebecryl-4690>

⁸ <https://allnex.com/en/product/216e16f3-e8e7-40e5-bc36-d7137495ef76/dpha>

⁹ <https://cdnsiencepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1139/v63-109>

Europe are Allnex, Sigma-Aldrich/Merck, and IGM Resins, but globally most producers are located in China.¹⁰ Two of the most profiled providers outside Europe are Longchang Chemicals (China) and HUPC Chemicals (headquartered in Hong Kong).

6.1.3 Other components (in both alternatives A and B)

Laromer PO77F is another energy curable resin, an oligomer. Laromers are widely used in industries such as printing and packaging, and adhesives, as well as coatings for various applications.¹¹ It is produced by one of the world's leading chemical corporations, which is headquartered in Germany, but running plants in 41 countries, and currently expanding in Asia.

TEGO® Airex 990 is a deaerator concentrate presented as highly compatible, with high effectiveness in solvent borne and high solids coatings, and very suitable for clear coats. The producer presents it as a "formulation based on deaerating organic polymers, with a tip of silicone". Tego Airex 990 is reported to have 50% biobased content.¹² The producer is based in Germany but is among the world leading actors in specialty chemicals, active in more than 100 countries.¹³

Jetfine 2 is a filler, with the chemical name magnesium silicate. It is an ultrafine talc produced from raw material sourced in Europe, which has a considerably lower carbon footprint (-73%) than its non-European equivalent Jetfine T3.¹⁴ This component is produced by a multinational originating from France, specialised in the production and processing of industrial minerals.

Acematt OK412 is a wax-treated, medium particle sized precipitated silica, serving as an all-purpose matting agent for coatings and overprint varnishes, which offers very high compatibility.¹⁵ Precipitated silica is produced by the controlled neutralization of dilute sodium silicate (waterglass) by either concentrated sulfuric, hydrochloric, or carbonic acids. The raw materials are those required for the silicate: sand, soda ash, caustic soda, and water,¹⁶ and the product is provided by one of the large German actors in the chemical industry.

¹⁰ Dipentaerythritol hexaacrylate | 29570-58-9 (chemicalbook.com)

¹²https://products.evonik.com/assets/57/79/Fact_Sheet_Biobased_Products_General_EN_Asset_835779.pdf

¹³ <https://www.evonik.com/en/company.html>

¹⁴ <https://www.imerys.com/product-ranges/jetfine>

¹⁵ ACEMATT_OK_412_TDS_EN_EN_TDS_PV_52043821_en_GB_WORLD.pdf (evonik.com)

¹⁶ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/engineering/precipitated-silica>

HF2086 is a type of hydrogen fluoride. Hydrogen fluoride is an inorganic compound with chemical formula HF. It is a very poisonous, colourless gas or liquid that dissolves in water to yield an aqueous solution termed hydrofluoric acid. It is the principal industrial source of fluorine, often in the form of hydrofluoric acid, and is an important feedstock in the preparation of many important compounds including pharmaceuticals and polymers.¹⁷ By 2022, the seven most highly rated hydrogen fluoride companies globally were Honeywell (US), Solvay (Belgium), Dongyue Group (China), Lanxess (Germany), Arkema (France), Sinochem (China), and Yingpeng Chemical (China).¹⁸

TEGO RAD 2500 is an efficient cross-linkable slip additive and defoamer for radiation-curing inks and varnishes. According to the chemical description, it is a radically cross-linkable siliconeacrylate, but the data sheet does not mention any biobased content.¹⁹

6.1.4 Conventional top coat formulation

The conventional UV-curable top coating considered for comparison, was also provided by September 2024, and characterised as follows (Table 4).

Table 4: Formulation for conventional top coat (September 2024).

Conventional top coat selected for comparison
Ebecryl 6000
TMP(EO)TA
DPGDA
Laromer PO77F
Tego Airex 990
Jetfine 2
Acematt OK412
HF2086
Tego Rad 2500

EBECRYL 6000 is a resin, an epoxy acrylate, and the biobased version of bisphenol A diglycidyl ether diacrylate (EBECRYL 600) containing ~22% biocarbon, used in energy-

¹⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hydrogen_fluoride

¹⁸ 7 Best Hydrogen Fluoride Companies - Verified Market Research

¹⁹ https://products.evonik.com/assets/or/Id/Rad_2500_TDS_EN_EN_TDS_PV_52003531_en_GB_WORLD.pdf

curing applications including coatings, inks and overprint varnishes. According to the producer, it includes up to 47% bio-carbon content, reducing GHG emissions by 29%.

TMP(EO)TA (Trimethylolpropane ethoxy triacrylate) is another monomer, commonly used in UV- and electron beam (EB) curable coatings and inks. TMPEOTA can be used to impart crosslinking to energy curable coatings and inks while maintaining a degree of flexibility and toughness.²⁰ Geographically, Asia-Pacific holds the largest market share, followed by North America and Europe. Some of the key actors are BASF SE (Germany), Sartomer (part of ARKEMA, headquartered in France), Evonik (Germany), Sigma-Aldrich/Merck, and Allnex (Germany).²¹

DPGDA (Dipropylene Glycol Diacrylate) is a difunctional reactive diluent that polymerizes when exposed to sources of free radicals. DPGDA is particularly useful in coatings and inks where improved flexibility and adhesion are desired in combination with good moisture resistance. Some of the major players identified in global market reports are Covestro (Germany), Ataman Chemicals (Turkey), IGM Resins (Netherlands), Eternal Materials (Taiwan), Nanjing SQS Chemical (China), Double Bond Chemical (Taiwan), Huateng Pharmaceuticals (China), Hubei Chushengwei Chemistry (China).²²

Laromer PO77F, which was briefly described above (section 6.1.3) is also included in the conventional UV-curable topcoat formulation considered in this SIA.

6.2 Potential impacts on value chain actors

6.2.1 Knowledge development

Knowledge development is assessed via two indicators: a) The level of knowledge development required to upscale the solutions, and b) the reported activity in research and development, and research and development collaboration, among relevant key actors.

Our mapping of the research, innovation and knowledge building activities among the sample actors (Annex A) shows that most of the big players have substantial expenditures on R&D. However, it is difficult to make direct comparisons, as some report as corporations

²⁰TMPEOTA - allnex

²¹<https://pmarketresearch.com/product/worldwide-ethoxylated-trimethylolpropane-triacrylate-tmpeota-market-research-2024-by-type-application-participants-and-countries-forecast-to-2030/>

²²Dipropyleneglycol Diacrylate (DPGDA) Market Size, Share, Growth & Trends [2023-2030] (verifiedmarketreports.com)

with a wide range of entities and business areas, while others report mainly on activity related to the coating industry. Among those providing information, some report collaboration with a wide range of research institutes, universities and alliances (e.g., around 200 in the case of E1). Some also state how much of their R&D is linked to biobased, more environment friendly, and or SDG aligned solutions, e.g., P2 has an ambition to increase their share of SDG aligned R&D from 52% currently, to 80% by 2025.

Furthermore, several actors are committed to sharing knowledge through Together for Sustainability.²³ On the other hand, there are also actors in the identified sample who do not provide any information about their R&D and knowledge collaboration, a finding indicating that they do give a high priority to knowledge sharing and joint effort to enable more sustainable solutions.

Considering the information obtained for the actors related to the respective components, and their average rating (1-3) for each of the considered coating formulations, we find limited variation. However, the new bio-based binders in Biobased Alternative A and biobased Alternative B are both associated with a high level of knowledge development, as they are provided by actors that have broad R&D collaboration in projects dedicated to bio-based innovation as their core activities. With projects that per definition aim at knowledge creation, the results (both direct and in form of tacit knowledge) from the ongoing technology development can also be transferred to other applications.

Moreover, we note a geographical dimension, in that the actors headquartered in Western countries tend to boast more co-development and sharing of knowledge, whereas those anchored in the far East appear more closed. That the key actors behind the two biobased alternatives are European owned, is thus another factor that can make for a higher impact in terms knowledge development, than what can be associated with the conventional formulation. Overall, we therefore give the biobased alternatives a higher score for this impact category.

The stakeholder interviews suggest that limited knowledge sharing among the industry actors working on bio-based solutions is a challenge, as this work usually is confidential. They also show that the knowledge level among the actors varies a lot, from very little to advanced. There is an urgent need for knowledge development, both with regard to the development of biobased coating solutions as such, and with regard to their sustainability.

²³ [Home - TFS Initiative \(tfs-initiative.com\)](https://www.tfs-initiative.com)

There are substantial knowledge gaps when it comes to environmental claims and ratings, and the requirements behind these. This is reflected in the scores, which are just above the medium-level impact 2, and not near 3 for any of the assessed alternatives.

6.2.2 Fair competition

Fair competition relates to the way actors operate regarding compliance with anti-corruption and competition laws (e.g., anti-trust regulations). This impact category is assessed via two indicators: a) the absence or presence of Codes of Conduct applying to suppliers, and b) the reported level of assessment and/or compliance among suppliers (see Annex B).

The industry actors usually address compliance with relevant anti-corruption and competition laws through stated Codes of Conduct, emphasising their dedication and compliance, illuminating available mechanisms for reporting breaches in their organisational systems, and their intent to promote the same dedication among their suppliers. Key principles related to fair competition (e.g., anti-corruption) are also anchored in universally legally binding instruments such as the UNs Convention against Corruption (2003), and promoted through the UN Global Compact initiative, which aims to ensure that anti-corruption principles are implemented as an inalienable part of sustainable businesses. Several of the key actors state their commitment to this initiative, and/or other frameworks to actively promote fair business practices.

Some actors have additional Codes of Conduct for their suppliers. However, the number of suppliers who sign these can vary. In addition to encouraging their suppliers to sign the respective Codes of Conduct, bigger actors conduct sustainability assessments of their suppliers as part of their procurement processes, for example, through Together for Sustainability. Other actors include clauses on their right to conduct audits (either themselves or involving third parties), as well potential sanctions for their suppliers in case of potential violations of human and labour rights.

It should be noted, however, that some of the sample actors do not have a Code of Conduct or explicit policy to promote fair competition. Those disclosing information about the share of suppliers assessed do also have a way to go before reaching 100%. These findings reflect statements from the interviews, suggesting that as the value chains for chemicals are highly complex and internationally dispersed, their level of transparency remains a subject to improvement. Interestingly, some interviewees noted that while the supply

chains behind established fossil-based products have had long time to prove their performance, biobased solutions only now enter this competition regime.

Still, suppliers of both fossil-based and biobased components are currently 1) bound by the respective national rules and laws on antitrust and trade regulations; and 2) put additional focus on ensuring fair competition through, e.g., Codes of Conduct, if the latter go beyond compliance. While there is considerable variation in how detailed the clauses on fair competition and follow-up procedures are, there are no clear differences between the findings for the three coating formulations. We therefore rate the social impact in this category as medium-level (2), both for the conventional coating and the novel bio-based formulations. This rating is based on the observed improvement potential, while acknowledging the efforts among leading actors to improve this aspect of corporate governance.

6.2.3 Sustainable product expansion

The focal biobased formulations are developed mainly to reduce and substitute the fossil-based content in high-volume ultraviolet (UV)-curable topcoats. However, the novel biobased components may also substitute components based on less sustainable biomass resources (e.g., food crops), and replace less sustainable components in other chemical products, either in themselves, or via by-products. Thus, upscaling of the novel, biobased UV-curable topcoats can be associated with a potential for sustainable product expansion, as a positive impact for the value chain actors. The relevant indicator, which potentially may be quantified, but we only can assess qualitatively at present is: The types and volume of non-sustainable products on the market that the biobased innovations potentially can replace.

Regarding Biobased Alternative A, poplar can be used to substitute for fossil feedstock in several value chains, including e.g., bioenergy and pharmaceuticals, as well as coatings (Hood et al., 2013). Previous research highlights the potential of natural products (phytochemicals) from poplar for new business ventures in biorefineries. Devappa et al. (2015) identified the potential pharmaceutical and other uses of > 160 phytochemicals identified from poplar species, while also discussing the related challenges and limitations (e.g., need for more research, and continuous supply of feedstock to generate industry interest), and opportunities, where consumer awareness and increasing demand for chemical compounds derived from natural products are highlighted.

Glyceryl Propoxy Triacrylate (GPTA) can be fossil-based, but is also increasingly produced from biomass, which is the glycerol is made from biobased resources, in most cases by-products from biofuel production. Samudrala (2019) discusses new valorisation technologies to produce high-value tonnage chemicals from glycerol via sustainable processes. Some of the important commodity chemicals associated with a considerable upscaling potential are propanediols, propanols and ethylene glycol (ibid.).

In Biobased alternative B, residues from forestry and wood processing industry in form of woodchips made of hardwood (birch) is the feedstock for the novel biobased component, based on cellobiose. According to the website of the producer, residual hardwood derived sugars are a sustainable alternative for the whole bioprocessing industry to produce many everyday used and platform chemicals.²⁴ Here, we are talking about two sugars, C5 Sugar, and C6 Sugar.

C5 Sugar, or xylose, is the main building block for the hemicellulose xylan, which comprises about 30% of some plants (such as birch), and far less in others (spruce and pine have about 9% xylan).²⁵ This can be fermented into products such as cellulosic ethanol, single cell protein, organic acids, fatty acids, or alkenes for cosmetics, and/or applied in the production of biofuels. C6 Sugar, or glucose, works as an ideal substitute for common agricultural sugars. It does not compete with food production and can be used in most fermentation processes for several bulk chemicals, personal care products, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals production.

These observations suggest that both of the biobased alternatives are associated with components that have a good potential for substituting fossil-based components, both in the target coating formulations, and also in other products. Their application in the studied focal solutions may stimulate production and thus provide a basis for development and use of these components in other products, where they can substitute for less sustainable materials. This potential could be slightly higher for Biobased Alternative A, to the extent that this alternative includes two new components with a substantial share of biobased content, from different feedstocks, whereas Biobased Alternative B, has one novel, biobased component, together with acrylated dipentaerythrinol (DPHA), which is not biobased. In both cases, the multiple options for substitution are associated with a potential for innovation and sustainable product expansion. We also reason that the multiple options

²⁴ <https://fibenol.com/products>

²⁵ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Xylose>

add to social sustainability, in the sense that actors will have several, different pathways open, and may shift from one to the other in future in case the market or framework conditions develop in uncondusive ways.

6.2.4 Green competitive advantage

The term “green competitive advantage” relates to a “condition under which companies occupy some positions about environmental protection or green innovation where their competitors cannot copy their successful environmental strategies, and they can gain the sustainable benefits from these successful environmental strategies” (Chen & Chang, 2011, p.532). Green competitive advantage can be measured along several dimensions, e.g., better quality of green products compared to the ones delivered by competitors, improvement of environmental image of the company compared to its competitors, company’s growth regarding green products etc. (ibid.).

The focal solutions are expected to have positive potential impact in this category, as working with biobased components in addition to the fossil-based ones allows the companies, in case of success, either to add a tangible product to their portfolio or replace some of the fossil-based products or components. At the same time, transparency and documentation of relevant sustainability aspects remains crucial for the ability to market new products as a part of the sustainability work of the companies. For the actors who base their activities solely on biobased components (e.g., supplier of biobased components in the focal solutions), the novel biobased solutions and knowledge accumulated through the work on their respective components have a positive impact in strengthening their position as a potential supplier of green components. Here, again it is necessary to document relevant sustainability aspects to ensure that these new components are sustainable.

This connects directly to the CSRD reporting some of the identified actors are subject to, as well as various voluntary sustainability reporting schemes applied in the coatings sector. Supplying, designing, producing or otherwise contributing to the development and diffusion of novel biobased coatings may have a positive impact on relevant rankings, e.g., GRI Index, EcoVadis, and environmental management standards (e.g., ISO14001), which can strengthen the actors’ position in the industry. We consider that the novel biobased formulation will be associated with benefits of this kind, to a greater extent than the conventional alternative.

6.3 Potential impacts on workers

6.3.1 Human rights

Human rights are central in the guidelines on S-LCA (UNEP, 2020), and labour rights is one of the four criteria set for the social sustainability of the bio-based part of bio-based products by the European Committee for Standardisation (CEN, 2016). Universally adopted principles, such as UN Global Compact labour principles to promote decent work, and the international labour standards of the International Labour Organization (ILO), as well as the OECD Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises and the Tripartite Declaration of Principles Concerning Multinational Enterprises and Social Policy (MNE Declaration) of the ILO provide a basis for improvement in this area, and are increasingly included in corporate Codes of Conduct (COC) (where such are explicitly defined) through actors' commitment to respect and promote human rights. The indicators we consider here are therefore a) the commitments stated in COCs and human rights policies, and b) the range of specific activities related to human rights reported by the sample actors.

Some of the actors considered extend their human rights commitment to explicit clauses that embrace active protection of human rights, organise audits to ensure their suppliers' commitments, put in place mechanisms enabling reporting of risks and violations and sometimes encourage their suppliers to promote similar routines throughout their respective value chains. Others address this aspect with the help of an internally established Human Rights Experts Group, indicating assigning resources to the topic. In their COCs for Suppliers some actors include possible sanctions for the suppliers in case of their failure to commit and ensure these principles in addition to their expectation to commit to and respect human rights in form of either immediate termination of their agreements in general or termination of agreements until the breaches or risks of violations have been addressed by the suppliers.

The interviews reveal that some actors expect this aspect to be adequately addressed through their compliance with respective laws, especially if their operations or suppliers' operations are located in Europe. While compliance with respective laws and regulations is expected, there is a difference in the level of detail in the openly available COCs regarding the sanctions that suppliers might face. Further, some actors in the industry do not have a COC openly available. However, big established actors recognise the importance of this aspect in their overall sustainability policies.

Further, human rights are considered in several of the sustainability ranking and reporting initiatives that are used in the chemical industry. Some of the interviewed actors use, for example, Eco Vadis for their own sustainability performance assessment, as well as in their work with suppliers. Labour&Human rights is one of the topics that can be selected for assessment in this framework. Furthermore, some of the key actors state an aim to procure raw materials more locally, and preferably in Europe, in future. To the extent that this is implemented, this could potentially have a positive impact on workers' rights, due to the presence of unified principles on Labour&Human rights (European Convention of Human Rights, Community Charter of the Fundamental Social Rights of Workers).

The varying scores in this category are explained by the availability of COCs and the level of detail in the clauses related to the aspect of human and labour rights (Annex C). The novel biobased solutions are expected to have at least the same impact in this regard.

6.3.2 Fair wages

"Fair wages" refers to the value of a service being reflected in the wage received (UNEP, 2021). Income and wages—but not necessarily if they are fair or not— is a commonly used subcategory in SIA of biobased value chains (Marting Vidaurre et al., 2020). Valente et al. (2018) emphasise that wages paid for a normal working week should meet at least the minimum wage, established either by law, collective bargaining agreement or an industry standard. We consider this as a distinct category, since the right to collective bargaining and commitment to support the principles of fair wages are highlighted in the policies and GRI reporting of several key actors, and there are differences in the level of articulation of suppliers' commitment to support these principles.

While some do not provide any information in this regard, others have articulated HR policies, include information about how many of their employees are covered by collective bargaining instruments, and require similar practices from their suppliers (e.g., F1 reports that 100% of their employees in Germany, and 70% of their employees worldwide, are covered by collective agreements on remuneration). A few actors set additional targets, for example J1 aims to extend the UN Living wage initiative to 100% of their employees by 2026).

Whereas the practices vary, we see no clear differences between the findings for the two biobased alternatives and the conventional topcoat formulation considered. The novel biobased binders are associated with European actors that may perform well and have a

positive effect for this social impact category, but as at now there is no information available on their practices in this area. We thus give the same score to the three alternatives for this impact category, expecting that this should be a focus area, independently of whether it relates to biobased or fossil-based coatings.

6.3.3 Equal opportunities

When it comes to equal opportunities, gender is the dimension most often addressed, in international indexes on working conditions and work environment. Hence this generally is the dimension of equality there is most data available for. However, this is another area with considerable variation in our sample. Some of the key actors report in detail and present specific measures to enhance gender equality, both in terms of recruitment, remuneration and career advancements. Diversity in terms of country of origin and language or ethnic group, is also reported by some companies. In a global industry dominated by large multinationals, this is also an important aspect, which should be given more attention in future. However, other actors do not provide the relevant information, neither on gender nor on other aspects related to diversity and inclusion.

For the present assessment, the proportion of women of the total workforce is selected as the main indicator for this subcategory. While a number of the relevant enterprises report on the share of women on their steering boards and management, this is not very consistent, and the definitions of management that are applied differ, e.g., some consider only executives, while others include administrative personnel at lower levels.

Since specific efforts to improve gender balance in employment are important, we also take the available information on this into account. The detailed findings from the review of actors' annual and sustainability reports are provided in Annex D. Overall, we find that there is limited information related to the two novel bio-based binders, and very varied reports related to GPTA, where those providing information on the share of women in the total workforce and at management level report relatively high percentages (e.g., up to 47% women in proportion to the total workforce) but the majority does not provide any information. In relation to DPHA we find a similar variation, whereas in relation to DPGDA four actors do not disclose the relevant information, and the two who do also report rather low percentages of female employees (that is, 17% and 23.2%, respectively). While these differences are interesting, there is too limited data and the difference is too small to be significant. We therefore consider the social impact for all the three formulations to be at

a similar level – medium (2) – as this is an area where continued improvement efforts should be made, but which also is in focus among key actors.

6.3.4 Health and safety

In a social sustainability assessment health and safety implications at multiple levels should ideally be covered, i.e. one should consider such impacts for consumers and users, as well as workers, and also take into consideration wider and more long-term effects, e.g., from leaching into the environment. Within PERFE COAT detailed analysis of such interactions has been a separate research task, but unfortunately findings are not ready and cannot be referenced in this SIA. Therefore, we consider health and safety mainly in relation to workers, based on the assessment of two indicators: 1) The health hazards reported for each component, or component type, in the relevant safety factsheets, and 2) the total recordable injury rate (TRIR) and reported incident rate (RIR), reported by the relevant actors.

Regarding hazards, there are no existing classifications for the novel, biobased binders yet. However, available information for xylose suggests that this substance in itself is associated with a low hazard for usual industrial handling. That is, it may cause eye, skin, and respiratory tract irritation.²⁶ For cellobiose, there are no known harmful effects, when used and handled according to specifications, and the substance is not subject to e.g., ECHA classification.²⁷

GPTA and Ebecryl 4690, as the other two components that are specific for Biobased Alternative A in this assessment, are also associated only with minor hazards, in form of possible allergic and general skin irritation, and serious eye irritation if protective equipment is not applied as recommended. The same is the case for DPHA, as the other component specific for Biobased Alternative B.

When it comes to the components that are included in the formulation for the conventional alternative, but not in the novel biobased formulations, Ebecryl 6000 may cause an allergic skin reaction. However, there is no harmonised classification and there are no notified hazards by manufacturers, importers or downstream users for TMP(EO)TA, according to

²⁶ <https://westliberty.edu/health-and-safety/files/2012/08/D-plus-or-minus-Xylose.pdf>

²⁷ <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Cellobiose#section=Hazard-Classes-and-Categories>

the ECHA database.²⁸ For DPGDA, possible skin irritation, allergic skin reaction and serious eye damage are noted, and the substance may be harmful if swallowed.

Among the components common to all three formulations, Tego RAD 2500 may cause an allergic reaction. For Acematt OK412 no SARA hazards are recorded, but it is noted that dust may cause some irritation, and could have a drying effect on the skin. The other components, included in small amounts, could have more serious health and safety impacts: For Laromer PO77F, suspicion of damaging fertility and damaging the unborn child are reported hazards. Tego Airex 990 may cause drowsiness or dizziness, be fatal if swallowed or entering airways, and possibly also damage the unborn child. HF2086 is associated with high risk, as it may be fatal if inhaled, swallowed or brought into contact with the skin, and also cause severe skin burns and eye damage. For Jetfine 2, we have not had a safety data sheet available, but talc in general can irritate the nose, throat and lungs. It is not classified with respect to cancer, and the need for further testing with respect to reproductive harm is noted.²⁹

Thus, the components associated with highest risk are common to the three alternatives assessed. Looking at the reported injury and incident rates, some of the key actors from the Far East do not provide much information, whereas the Western corporations behind the components that are specified as a particular, registered products tend to perform well. Jetfine 2 is an exception associated with a relatively high Total Recordable Incidents Rate (TRIR) (2.19), which may be due to the nature of quartz mining. Otherwise, there is no clear pattern in the variation (for details, see Annex E). While the hazards noted for specific components may not influence the health and safety performance of the final formulations, these findings suggest that the health and safety of workers is a social hotspot, or risk area, for the biobased as well as the conventional alternatives. At the same time, most of the key actors emphasize health and safety in their sustainability reporting and continuous improvement work, and we would rate the overall impact as medium-level (2).

²⁸ Substance Information - ECHA (europa.eu)

²⁹ <https://nj.gov/health/eoh/rtkweb/documents/fs/1773.pdf>

6.4 Potential impacts on local communities

6.4.1 Green value creation

Value creation is often considered in social sustainability assessments, and other studies (e.g., Brinkman et al., 2019) have used gross value-added as an indicator for this. However, macro-economic analysis is difficult for early-stage innovations like those considered here, and figures would be highly uncertain. Some general assumptions and arguments can still be made, based on the information available.

As noted above, Biobased Alternative A is based on short coppice poplar. Poplar is considered as a good biorefinery feedstock because of year-round availability and ease of fractionation, but still of limited availability and associated with high costs. In terms of socio-economic impacts (multiplier effects), using of purpose-grown such as poplar as feedstock for biobased products will generate somewhat higher value added than residues, as dedicated crops for biomass carry higher costs than utilization of residues. The latter assumption is aligned with the life-cycle cost (LCC) assessment in PERFECOAT, finding that at the present stage of development, Biobased Alternative A is associated with higher costs than Biobased Alternative B.³⁰

In a study on poplar grown for biomass energy production in Miajadas, Spain, local stakeholders highlighted multiple socioeconomic benefits; in particular local employment creation, rural reactivation, economic diversification, and increase in local investments. They also indicated that there were positive impacts in terms of preservation of natural heritage and environmental awareness (Damman and Rodrigues, 2015). Poplar may also be used to provide ecosystem services in water management, e.g., for riparian buffers or phytoremediation. Recent research indicates that including poplar used for wastewater treatment can reduce the cost of poplar as feedstock significantly, and at the same time provide value for local communities both related to the biobased product and the ecosystem services provided (Chowyuk et al., 2021).

Considering GPTA, glycerol is currently provided as a by-product from biodiesel and oleochemicals. Both of these industries are likely to experience growth in future, in line with increasing decarbonisation efforts and decline in oil and gas production. Indeed, the expected growth in world-wide production of glycerol is strong, hence utilizing it as a raw

³⁰ Azrague, K., Hung, C.R. (2024). Report on comparative LCA and LCC, including end-of-life strategies. Deliverable 6.2, PERFECOAT (confidential).

material for sustainable is vitally important (Kaur et al., 2020). Use of glycerin as a platform chemical to make higher valued derivatives is therefore associated with a considerable value creation potential (Pagliaro, 2017). Samudrala (2018) is one study suggesting that high-value tonnage chemicals from glycerol can be developed via sustainable processes such as oxidation, dehydration, hydrogenolysis, steam reforming, carboxylation, acetalization, esterification and chlorination. Propanediols, propanols and ethylene glycol are some of those considered promising in future. However, it is also noted that in future, the value creation from any bio-based product will depend on a) feedstock cost and availability, b) efficiency of the conversion process used to upgrade it, and c) value of the biobased product (ibid.).

Regarding Biobased Alternative B, the concept of circular bioeconomy based on residues from forestry and wood processing has been well received by industry (Korhonen et al., 2018a). In Northern Europe, several of the large incumbents in the sector increasingly work to integrate circular elements into their business portfolio and operations, while small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are emerging with new sustainability-driven business models (ibid.). Research on these changes is still scant, but several studies suggest that they are associated with a considerable value creation potential.

D'Amato et al. (2020), in a Finnish study, found that raw materials, technological know-how and/or partnership were critical for value creation and delivery. Companies dealing with high value-added products were at advantage, as they need relatively small amounts of raw material. Several companies were based on innovative technology development, but compatibility with existing processes and facilities tended to be an advantage. Moreover, outsourcing services and developing new value chains with stakeholders, and co-operation with research and international partners were important (ibid.). In terms of value capture for societal actors, job creation, improved quality of life, and reduced social and environmental impact in production and over the total life cycle of the products were noted. Meanwhile, the existing research literature also shows that local value capture depends on pre-existing structures and capabilities (Paletto et al., 2021).

A recent case study on potential impacts of establishing a fast pyrolysis plant with novel technology for production of advanced biofuel and by-products that may be used as platform chemicals (Damman et al., 2024) indicates positive social impacts at the local level, both in terms of value creation, employment, wellbeing and innovation capacity. However, these depend on the size of plant and availability of feedstock and may not be

as big as the most ardent circular bioeconomy proponents claim, and at the national level, these benefits are partly outweighed by decline in the value chains behind the substituted products.

Thus, the novel biobased UV-curable topcoats are associated with a considerable value creation potential. With the feedstocks currently considered, this would be higher for Biobased Alternative A, than for Biobased Alternative B, but there is a high level of uncertainty.

6.4.2 Support for community development

As social sustainability increasingly is emphasized in policy and sustainability reporting, most of the large actors in the chemical industry address impacts on local communities in their CSR policies. The Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) approach, recommended by the European Commission as a voluntary approach to guide the innovation process for chemicals and materials, also includes addressing socio-economic sustainability as an optional step. However, a finding from the stakeholder interviews is that the effort to contribute positively to local community development in practice remains limited, and not well documented. Under this impact category, two indicators were considered: a) support for community welfare, in terms of funding, and b) activity or spending on community engagement.

The review of online documents available regarding the sample actors confirmed that the level of documentation is variable. For the actors behind the novel biobased binders, which still are rather small enterprises, no information on community support or other CSR activities was available. While some larger actors also provided no information on this, the majority did. Most of the reported activity takes the form of donations, mostly for education, culture, and health. While some companies (e.g., F1) focus mainly on activities in the mother country, others (e.g., G1) rather target the population in the most disadvantaged communities where they are active.

One trend seems to be that actors headquarters in the Far East tend to focus on donations and extended welfare arrangements, e.g., for retired workers, whereas many of the larger actors headquartered in Europe increasingly emphasize community engagement, partly to promote their own interests and standing in the communities, but also to stimulate local development, e.g. one (J1) takes a "Common Ground" approach to build relationships with local industrial systems and engage local actors in "ChemArt Green Innovation Classes",

and another (N3) runs an Intrapreneurship program, including a Starting Ventures activity targeting low-income areas. Annex F provides a summary of actors' community support or CSR activities.

These developments are important, especially in areas where chemical industrial activity also has or have had adverse local impacts. In relation to hydrogen fluoride, recent literature (Rizzu et al., 2021) shows that crops exposed to soil and water fluoride pollution may reach concentrations of fluoride that potentially are harmful to humans, and that we still lack knowledge on such interactions. In relation to quartz mining, A study of the social and environmental impacts of mining activities in the EU (Mononen et al., 2022), shows that mining in some cases is seen as a threat to the local community and quality of life. Moreover, a local community can become too dependent on mining activities, leading to severe consequences once an all-important mine is closed, and the legitimacy of certain mining activities are questioned, due to lack of information and consultation (ibid.).

6.5 Potential impacts on consumers

6.5.1 Transparency

Transparency reflects the openness and availability of information about actors' activities that allows others to observe, follow and assess these activities. Sufficient transparency enables an informed choice for the consumer, and includes information regarding social responsibility, as documented in the form of standards or labels (UNEP, 2021). It has previously been assessed e.g., in terms of the "existence of public sustainability reporting" and the "availability of public documents on agreements to sustainability issues" (Groiß-Fürtner et al., 2023). In our case, the potential impact of the novel biobased coating solutions, and the conventional coating alternative using similar indicators, that is the online availability of annual/financial reports, and sustainability reports or articulated sustainability policies, but also consider the available product information, in form of technical data sheets (TDS) and safety data sheets (SDS). An overview of the information found is provided in Annex G.

Overall, the sampled actors operate with varying level of transparency. While the majority make annual financial reports available online, there are also a substantial share that do not. The latter is more common among the companies headquartered in the Far East, reflecting that transparency is influenced by regulations and local norms, as well as

business policies concerning corporate decision-making and operations openness. In most cases, those sharing annual financial reports also provide sustainability reports, either integrated with the annual report, or as a separate document. However, in some cases the access to the sustainability reports is restricted to a limited (e.g., G1). Further, some suppliers report on the sustainability of their activities without their annual reports being available (C3, L3).

There are also big differences with regard to the availability of product information. In many cases both TDS and SDS are openly available, but it is also quite common that customers must register or submit an enquiry to get access to these documents. In some cases, they are not at all available. Notably, this is the case for all the actors considered in relation to HF2086, which happens to be the component (included in all the three topcoat formulations considered) which is associated with the most serious health hazards (see section 6.3.4.). Overall, given the lack of annual reports and/or sustainability reports by suppliers of components in the biobased alternatives, as well as currently limited availability of the product information due to their development stage, we assign lower score in this impact category to the biobased alternatives compared to the fossil-based reference coating.

6.5.2 Wellbeing – from buying more sustainable products

Wellbeing is an aspect of the quality of life, referring to what is intrinsically valuable relative to someone, e.g., associated with positive experience and self-interest. So, the wellbeing of a person is what is ultimately good for this person. Wellbeing, in this sense, is related to non-monetary value, such as moral and existential value, and so-called bequest value, connected with the preservation of natural and/or cultural resources, for the benefit of future generations. Novel biobased products may have a positive impact along these lines, e.g., previous research has found that consumers linked biobased paint to the environment and thought of it as better than regular paint for their own health and that of the children, as well as more “natural” and environment friendly (Sijtsema et al., 2016).

On the other hand, we noted above (chapter 5) that consumer wellbeing may be influenced negatively via cost and negative associations related to distrust (ibid.). The share of biobased material would also matter – when the percentage is very low, some consumers raised questions about the motivations of the producer (greenwashing), whereas a higher percentage of biobased content was seen as positive. In addition to these factors, D’Amato

et al. (2020), note that increased consumption choices for users and customers can be considered as a social benefit in itself.

6.6 Potential impacts on wider society

6.6.1 Land use and food security

Social science research on the bioeconomy stresses that sustainability assessment of biobased products must consider global net sustainability, including possible problem shifting, cascade and rebound effects, as well as other unexpected and undesirable impacts (Liobikiene et al., 2019; D'Amato and Korhonen, 2021). Within this wide and long-term picture, land use is a key issue. A comprehensive analysis of economic trends in the transition to a circular bioeconomy (Kircher, 2022a) argues that as more sectors, including energy production and organic chemistry is integrated, how to meet their raw material requirements will be a challenge. There is not enough knowledge on whether and to what extent the production of biomass in Europe can be expanded in a sustainable manner, within planetary boundaries, ecosystem service capacities and taking into account the consequences of climate change (ibid.).

Against this background, our assessment of potential impact in this category includes considerations of 1) whether the biomass used in the solutions can be used for food production); 2) whether the land use for feedstock production potentially could impact negatively on food security or biodiversity; 3) whether other input materials for the coating solutions can cause land deterioration in a long-term perspective.

Considering Biobased Alternative A, poplar, as the feedstock for the novel biobased binder, is widely promoted as a short rotation coppices (SRC) crop for the bioeconomy. In contrast to large tree plantations threatening biodiversity in the tropics, site-adapted species of poplar in temperate zones, with disturbed land that needs remediation and/or underutilised land resources, can enhance sustainability in terms of reducing flooding, nutrient export, and soil erosion. However, a key challenge is competition for cultivated land, which will increase in future (Meyer et al., 2021). Similar concerns were raised in the interviews, where the origin of biomass for the biobased solutions and potential land use conflicts in future were mentioned as critical factors. Communicating and documenting the origin of biomass is necessary to ensure a good foundation for assessing the social impact of the biobased coating solutions on land use and food security. These concerns were echoed by an expert interviewed by European Coatings, claiming that currently, the agricultural

surface occupied with plants for biobased products is below 1 %, and even with the most positive projections, this space may increase only to 5 % by 2027. With a view to security of supply, he suggested that suppliers to the coatings industry should focus on byproducts and waste from the food industry to avoid competition and collaborate with third party organisations such as the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) to ensure that value chains operate sustainably.³¹

For the GPTA in the Biobased Alternative A, and also for the Ebecryl 6000, in the conventional formulation, the source of biomass is not specified and could be conflicting with food security and/or conservation of biodiversity in a short- or longer-term perspective. Thus, Biobased Alternative A is given the lowest score for this impact category. The conventional alternative, which contains a component with some biobased content of unspecified origin, scores slightly higher, whereas Bio B, with biobased content mainly from residues from forestry and wood processing has the higher score, highlighting that the origin of the biomass in bio-based products is crucial.

6.6.2 Substitution

According to international market reports, the market for UV-curable coatings is increasing sharply, especially in the European and North American coating industries. Globally, the estimated growth rates range from 5.2%,³² to 9.6%,³³ to 12%,³⁴ and the market is expected to reach USD 11.4 billion by 2025, USD 13.1 by 2028, and around USD 20 billion by 2031. While we do not have any market projections or estimates for the solution developed within PERFE COAT as such, these trends give reason to assume a good potential for the developed formulations to substitute for conventional, fossil-based alternatives.

On the other hand, it is important to remember that the biobased content remains limited, even if the target 25% or more has been met. LCA analyses carried out by SINTEF Community suggest that at the present stage of development, Biobased Alternative A has a biobased content of around 27%, while the biobased content in Biobased Alternative B is around 34%. Moreover, the conventional topcoat formulation, considered for comparison, also has a biobased content, of around 10%.³⁵

³¹<https://www.european-coatings.com/news/markets-companies/bio-based-coating-albeit-challenges-optimism-prevails/>

³²UV Coatings Market Outlook, Trends & Forecast by 2033 | FMI (futuremarketinsights.com)

³³ Global UV Curable Coatings Market Research & Growth Analysis (bccresearch.com)

³⁴ UV Curable Coatings Market Size, Industry Share Forecast Trends Report, [Latest] (marketsandmarkets.com)

³⁵ Azrague, K., Hung, C.R. (2024). Report on comparative LCA and LCC, including end-of-life strategies. Deliverable 6.2, PERFE COAT (confidential).

Thus, the new formulations do not represent 100% biobased products replacing a conventional product that is 100% fossil-based, but they can nevertheless make a significant contribution towards substitution and eventual phase-out of fossil-based materials from the coating industry, thereby contributing towards realisation of EU and national sustainability transition policies.

6.6.3 Circularity - making use of waste

While circular economy encompasses several strategies, its main principles are creating value by extending the life cycle of products and reducing waste to a minimum. In this SIA, we consider the amount of waste reduced by integration of biobased feedstocks as a relevant indicator for the stakeholder category Wider society. Value creation has already been addressed in relation to Local communities, and a detailed analysis of material circularity as such falls under environmental rather than social sustainability assessment.

As noted above, the novel, biobased binder in Biobased Alternative A is based on SRC poplar produced specifically to provide biomass, and not on residues. However, a significant share of the biobased content in Biobased Alternative A consists of GPTA. While the GPTA ingredients may vary from supplier to supplier, we may assume that it stems from biowaste, especially when taking a long-term perspective. In this case, full scale production of Biobased Alternative A would make a modest, but significant contribution towards the reduction of waste and transition towards a circular economy. Biowaste from agro-industrial activities is still under-utilized, and biowaste also constitutes a substantial fraction of the municipal solid waste stream, especially in developing countries (Kee et al., 2021). While traditional recovery methods such as composting and animal feed are used, and energy recovery in form of biogas increasingly is implemented, only around 25% of the total global biowaste is recycled (Razza et al., 2018).

In Biobased Alternative B, the novel, bio-based binder, as noted above, is based on residues from forestry and wood processing industry, and the share of biobased content is higher than in Biobased Alternative A, suggesting that the share of waste that is utilized is substantially higher in this case.

Although the conventional topcoat formulation considered in this SIA also has a share of biobased content, this is smaller. For Ebecryl 6000, as the relevant component, we do not know the exact source of the biobased content, (the technical data sheet does not reveal

this information) but the producer states that they generally source from second generation feedstock, as byproducts/residues from forestry, agriculture, industry or waste streams, while also evaluate sources that use regenerative agricultural and forestry practices. Thus, we cannot know if there will be a reduction of waste associated with the integration of biobased content in this alternative. At best, there will be a small contribution towards reducing waste for this alternative as well, but this will be smaller than for the novel, biobased formulations.

6.7 Chapter summary

This chapter has presented the focal solutions and findings from the SIA, distinguishing between social impacts for different stakeholder categories. For each stakeholder category, several impact categories and indicators were considered. The assessment suggests that the novel biobased formulations for UV-curable topcoats can be associated with positive social impacts along multiple dimensions. However, there are also certain areas with a risk of adverse impacts. In the following chapter, we provide a summary overview of the potential social impacts for each of the assessed coating formulations, and a brief discussion of the implications of the findings. Here, we also take into account the findings from the social acceptance study (chapter 5).

7 Overall assessment of potential social impacts

The findings presented in the previous chapter can be summarised and visualised as patterns of potential impacts for each of the assessed coating formulations (Figures 2, 3, 4). The patterns emerge from the ordinal ranking system described in section 4.3, were score 1 = least positive impact (blue), score 2 = medium impact (light green), and score 3 = most positive/least negative impact (dark green).

	Impact categories	Novel binder	GPTA	EBECRYL 4690	Laromer PPO77F	Tego Airex 990	Jetfine 2 (talc)	Acematt OK412	HF2086	Tego RaD 2500
Value chain	Knowledge development	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Fair competition	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Sust. product expansion	3	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	1
	Green advantage	3	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	1
Workers	Human rights	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	2	3
	Fair wages	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Equal opportunities	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Injury or incident rate	2	2	3	3	3	2	3	2	3
	Hazards	2	2	2	1	1	1	3	1	3
Local comm.	Green value creation	3	3	2	1	2	1	1	1	1
	Local CSR activities	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Consumers	Transparency	1	1	3	3	3	2	3	1	2
	Wellbeing	3	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	1
Wider society	Land use	1	1	1	3	1	1	3	3	3
	Waste reduction	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	1
	Substitution	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1

Figure 2: Overall assessment for Biobased Alternative A.

	Impact categories	Novel binder	DPHA	Laromer PPO77F	Tego Airex 990	Jetfine 2	Acematt OK412	HF2086	Tego RaD 2500
Value chain	Knowledge development	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Fair competition	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Sust. product expansion	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
	Green advantage	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
Workers	Human rights	2	2	3	3	3	3	2	3
	Fair wages	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Equal opportunities	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Injury or incident rate	2	2	3	3	2	3	2	3
	Hazards	2	2	1	1	1	3	1	3
Local comm.	Green value creation	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
	Local CSR activities	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Consumers	Transparency	2	2	3	3	2	3	1	2
	Wellbeing	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
Wider society	Land use	2	3	3	1	1	3	3	3
	Waste reduction	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
	Substitution	3	1	1	2	1	1	1	1

Figure 3: Overall assessment for Biobased Alternative B.

	Impact categories	Ebecryl 6000 (EA)	TMPEOTA	DPGDA	Laromer PPO77F	Tego Airex 990	Jetfine 2 (talc)	Acematt OK412	HF2086	Tego RaD 2500
Value chain	Knowledge development	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Fair competition	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Sust. product expansion	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
	Green advantage	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
Workers	Human rights	3	2	2	3	3	3	3	2	3
	Fair wages	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Equal opportunities	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Injury or incident rate	3	2	2	3	3	2	3	2	3
	Hazards	2	2	2	1	1	1	3	1	3
	Green value creation	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
Local comm.	Local CSR activities	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
	Transparency	3	2	2	3	3	2	3	1	2
Consumers	Wellbeing	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
	Land use	1	3	3	3	1	1	3	3	3
Wider society	Waste reduction	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
	Substitution	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Figure 4: Overall assessment for the conventional coating formulation.

The patterns exhibited in the figures are relatively similar, due to the fact that many of the components and the actors potentially supplying them are the same, for all the three coating formulations considered. However, there are also important differences. For the value chain actors, the novel formulations are associated with positive impacts, both in terms of knowledge development, potential for sustainable product expansion, and green competitive advantage. While no variation is discerned for fair competition, we still include this impact category, as a central aspect of the social sustainability of global value chains, interacting with other aspects of sustainability. The score 2 is given, across the board, to

signify that this is an area where substantial challenges remain, but also acknowledging that many of the key actors are working actively for improvement in this area.

For workers, there is little difference across the three formulations, but still some important points to note. The score 2 is much used, due to the high level of variation in actors' reporting. For human rights, fair wages and equal opportunities, many of the key actors disclose relevant information and reportedly take specific steps to improve their social footprint. However, there are also key actors who do not report on these dimensions publicly. We also find substantial variation between those who do report (e.g., from 15% to 47.1% of women in proportion to total workforce). This seems to be linked to where the production activities take place geographically, as well as corporate policies, and there is no systematic variation across components or formulations. Where the score 3 is applied, the formulations include specific products, with suppliers that are among those reporting best performance.

When it comes to health and safety of workers, the novel biobased binders are given the score 2, since there is the need for further documentation and no formal information on hazards, incidents, or injury rates are publicly available, but the existing documentation on xylose and cellobiose does not give reason to assume any severe risks. Components that are specific products without serious hazards and with suppliers that perform well in terms of reported incident and/or injury rates are given the score 3 for this impact category. However, several of the components applied in all the three formulations, are associated with serious health hazards and therefore given the score 1. Thus, health and safety of workers may be classified as a social hotspot, with uncertainty and risk that must be taken into account in further efforts to develop and promote the focal innovations.

Social impacts for local communities are difficult to assess, for early-stage innovations with the level of complexity that coating formulations have. However, we note a level of green value creation that is higher for Biobased Alternative A, which has a novel biobased binder associated with higher feedstock costs than Biobased Alternative B, as well as another component with a substantial share of biobased content and a different supply chain. In terms of CSR activities, less is reported for the novel biobased components, which are related to relatively small innovator enterprises, and the overall score for the biobased formulations is therefore slightly lower than for the conventional one.

In relation to consumers, the novel biobased formulations score slightly lower than the conventional formulation, due to unavailability of annual financial and sustainability supporting for the novel, biobased binders, and less product information available. There is also less transparency surrounding GPTA, than surrounding the other components, which gives a slightly lower average score for Biobased Alternative A, than for Biobased Alternative B. Still, as noted in the preceding chapter, there is reason to assume that the current documentation and reporting requirements for novel biobased products are likely to give a positive impact here in a longer-term perspective, when the innovations are further developed and introduced to the market. As the figures illustrate, we also find potential positive impacts on consumer wellbeing, linked to increased consumer choice and satisfaction from buying products associated with a higher level of sustainability.

When it comes to the wider society, the figures highlight potential impacts related to land use, where Biobased Alternative A has more components with biobased content that can be associated with potential conflicts linked to land use, food security and biodiversity than Biobased Alternative B, where the novel, biobased binder is based on residues. Score 1 is given for the components with biobased content from dedicated biomass crops or unspecified sources, but also for the Jetfine 2, which is a talc associated with mining of quartz. Score 2 is used for the biobased binder based on residues from forestry and wood processing, since increasing demand could lead to more intensive forestry with increased land use and negative impacts on biodiversity in a long-term perspective. Conventional components not associated without such land use issues are given the score 3. Overall, the risks related to land use, food security and conservation constitute another social hotspot, underscoring that feedstock origin is crucial for the social sustainability of biobased products.

Finally, Figures 2,3 and 4 illustrate the potential impacts in terms of waste reduction and substitution of fossil-based materials, where the novel biobased solutions are associated with more positive social impacts than the conventional alternative. Biobased Alternative B scores higher than Biobased Alternative A because it has a higher share of biobased content and is based on feedstock from residues.

The average results per stakeholder category are visualised below (Figure 5). The scores in the bar chart are based on calculation of the average scores for each impact category, which subsequently are combined for each stakeholder category.

Figure 5: Average results per stakeholder category.

When the results for the different impact categories are combined, some of the variation and most significant benefits and risks fall out of sight. However, Figure 5 also reflects what we noted above, that many of the components and suppliers remain the same across the three formulations assessed. Still, we observe that the novel, biobased alternatives are associated with positive social impacts for local communities and consumers, as well as the value chain actors. Substantial benefits can also be expected at a wider society level, but here the long-term risks associated with land use, food security and biodiversity bring in uncertainty and lower scores, even if the focal feedstocks do not compete with food production presently. For workers, the results are similar across the three alternatives, as there is limited information for the novel biobased binders, remaining challenges in terms of human rights, fair wages and gender balance, and common health and safety risks associated with components that are present in all of them.

As our findings demonstrate, relevant information and documentation that could provide a better basis for assessment of social impacts is in some cases lacking. This challenge may gradually be reduced, given the increasing focus on social sustainability reporting in the EU. This may further strengthen the social acceptance of novel bio-based coating innovations, by illuminating potential positive impacts, while increasing the pressure on actors to better address identified social risks. These interactions may be crucial for the further development and diffusion of the solutions, as not only socio-political and community acceptance, but also market acceptance is influenced by perceptions of risk

and social norms (Huijts et al., 2012). As we have shown, consumer wellbeing is a crucial factor, and values such as diversity, inclusion and integrity are increasingly integrated into business transactions, via initiatives such as EcoVadis, Integrity Next, Together for Sustainability, and others.

Further, our findings support earlier research highlighting the need to select impact categories and indicators suited to the case and the context, as well as the importance of interaction with the stakeholders (Falcone et al., 2019; Rafiaani et al., 2019; Siebert et al., 2018b). Addressing context- and solution-specific sustainability aspects at an early stage in technological innovation is necessary to enhance the development and diffusion of the focal solutions. Consideration of both short-term and long-term impacts is crucial, to ensure local as well as global net sustainability. As illustrated in some of the reviewed literature (e.g., Liobikiene et al., 2019; D'Amato & Korhonen, 2021; Kircher, 2022), this is especially important in the case of biobased solutions, where the access to biomass can be uncertain and changing over time.

8 Conclusion

The study on social acceptance and potential social impacts of novel biobased coatings in PERFECOAT was carried out in two main steps. When the social acceptance study was conducted, the final formulations selected for assessment were not yet available.

The stakeholder interviews show that the socio-political acceptance of bio-based coatings is high, given the societal goals of decarbonisation and transition towards a more circular economy. In recent years, the EU has implemented many conducive policies, and The Transition Pathway for the EU Chemicals Industry indicates a growing commitment also in the industry. In terms of market acceptance, requirements from one key customer have been the main driver for increased biobased content in high-volume UV-curable clearcoats, and there is increasing interest in biobased solutions. However, questions regarding the functionality and wider impacts of such solutions remain. High costs still represent a challenge, and the willingness to invest is influenced by geopolitical uncertainties, and limited knowledge. Some stakeholders suggest that clearer targets and requirements are needed to accelerate the development and uptake of biobased solutions. Concerning community acceptance, lack of knowledge and awareness is also a challenge. To increase the level of acceptance among consumers, the development of coherent product concepts, demonstrating positive impact on both environmental and social sustainability, is important. This requires increased transparency, in line with recent policy and regulatory developments.

The social impact assessment was based on a review of annual, financial and sustainability reporting among key actors, in addition to the stakeholder interviews and a survey among project partners. The final formulations for UV-curable topcoats were selected as the focal solutions, in comparison with a conventional alternative. The results identify two main risk areas or social hotspots: In a short-term perspective, health and safety of workers is an area where there are remaining uncertainties and concerns. In a long-term perspective, potential land use conflicts linked to food security and biodiversity represent another social risk area, even if the poplar and wood residues utilised as feedstock are not associated with such conflicts today.

The novel bio-based topcoat formulations also score somewhat lower on transparency than the conventional alternative. However, they may have a positive impact over time, since they face comprehensive documentation requirements and sustainability will be a key

value proposition. Consumers will benefit in terms of increased choice and wellbeing. For local communities, green value creation and employment effects are foreseen, and for the value chain actors, benefits in terms of knowledge development, green competitive advantage and opportunities for sustainable product expansion can be anticipated. However, the focal solutions are at an early stage of development. Their contribution to sustainability will depend on the source of feedstock, functionality, wider impacts, and social acceptance, in a changing global context. This underscores the complexity of social impacts, and the need to consider this dimension as an integral part in technological innovation processes.

Limited data availability and the low TRL of the focal solutions has made this work challenging. However, the findings are in line with previous research, and the study sheds new light on the complex interaction between technology development, social acceptance, and potential social impacts of biobased innovations in the coating industry.

9 List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CEPE	The European Council of the Paint, Printing Ink, and Artist's Colours Industry
COC	Code of Conduct
CSRD	Corporate Social Reporting Directive
DIY	Do-it-yourself
EB	Electron beam
ECHA	European Chemical Agency
EPF	European Panel Federation
ESG	Environment, Social, and Governance (investing)
ESRS	European Sustainability Reporting Standards
GHG	Green House Gases
GRI	Global Reporting Initiative (standard)
ILO	International Labour Organisation
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
LTIR	Lost Time Injury Rate
OECD	Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
PTFE	Polytetrafluoroethylene
REACH	Regulation on the registration, evaluation, authorisation and restriction of chemicals
RIR	Recordable Injury Rate (OSHA)
RSPO	Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil
SASB	Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB)
SBTi	Science Based Targets initiative
SCOC	Supplier Code of Conduct
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SDS	Safety Data Sheet

SFDR	Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation
SHE	Safety, Health and Environment
SIA	Social Impact Assessment
SLCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SRC	Short Rotation Coppices
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Math
TDS	Technical Data Sheet
TfS	Together for Sustainability
TRIR	Total Recordable Incidents Rate
UV	Ultra Violet
VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds
WBCSD	World Business Council for Sustainable Development
WtP	Willingness to Pay

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Annex A: R&D and knowledge sharing

Component	R&D emphasized in reports	Knowledge sharing
Novel biobased binder (from xylose)	A1: R&D projects (EU), is a main part of the activity	A1: Through projects Lab, analyses, and online database as services
Novel biobased binder (from cellobiose)	B1: A broad range of R&D projects, main part of the activity (but also own production plant)	Via research project collaborations
GPTA	<p>C1: Science and Lab unit invested tens of millions EUR on R&D facilities in 2023, targeting biotech and pharmaceuticals EUR 2.4 billion for R&D in 2023</p> <p>C2: Website mentions own research, but not expenditure or ambitions.</p> <p>C3: Website presents R&D and boasts of patents in 2023, but is not specific on numbers</p> <p>C4: >180,000 annual research interactions, market research methodologies and innovation platforms in all regions</p> <p>C5: own scientific journal,</p> <p>C6: No info.</p> <p>C7: R&D services, at the core</p>	<p>C1: not specific on this, but mentions multi-disciplinary and focus on digital enablers</p> <p>C2: No info.</p> <p>C3: Collaboration with other large actors</p> <p>C4: Broad, only described in general terms</p> <p>C5: Collaboration with universities around the world</p> <p>C6: No info.</p> <p>C7: R&D services, collaboration with customers and in projects</p>
Ebecryl 4690	<p>D1: 23 research and technology support centers globally,</p> <p>Recent main research centre for sustainable coatings in Austria</p>	D1: JV with 5 world-class companies in Asia
Laromer PO77F	<p>E1: Innovation at the core of strategy, own research department</p> <p>Around 1000 new patents in 2023</p> <p>€2.1 bn expenses for R&D in 2023</p> <p>4,029 employees in R&D 2023</p>	<p>E1: World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD)</p>

		Nova-Institute’s Renewable Carbon Initiative Collaboration with around 200 research partners (universities, institutes, alliances)
Tego Airex 990	F1: €443 million in R&D in 2023 227 new patents in 2023 Own strategic innovation unit and business incubator.	F1: Partnerships with universities and research institutions across Europe, Asia, North America
Jetfine 2*	G1: Technology Centers in USA, China, UK, Switzerland, Austria, France. More than 50 new mineral solutions launched in 02023 (78% “SustainAgility solutions”)	G1: universities and external institutes in Europe and the USA
Acematt OK412	H1: €443 million in R&D in 2023 227 new patents in 2023 Own strategic innovation unit and business incubator	H1: Partnerships with multiple universities and research institutions across Europe, Asia, North America
HF2086	J1:28 patents, 6 major R&I centres, 40 mill EUR R&I 2023 J2: \$1,456 million R&D in 2023 J3: 107.18M (2023), Research for circularity, product safety, etc- J4: mainly in R&D production of new environmentally friendly refrigerants, fluorinated polymer materials, organosilicon materials, chlor alkali ion membranes and hydrogen fuel proton exchange membranes. J5: >200 patents in 2023 (90% related to sustainable development), 1800 researchers in 17 R&D centres.	J1: Amongst other with the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) on chemical research and its use in industry, goal to develop disruptive solutions. J2: Not specified. J3: Not specified. J4: No info. J5: Not specified.
Tego RAD 2500	K1: €443 million in R&D in 2023 227 new patents in 2023 Own strategic innovation unit and business incubator.	K1: Partnerships with multiple universities and research institutions across Europe, Asia, North America

<p>DPHA</p>	<p>L1: 23 research and technology support centers globally, Recent main research centre for sustainable coatings in Austria L2: Own R&D department L3: Website presents R&D and boasts of patents in 2023, but is not specific on numbers L4: Science and Lab unit invested tens of millions EUR on R&D facilities in 2023, targeting biotech and pharmaceuticals L5: Not specific on R&D, knowledge</p>	<p>L1; JV with 5 world-class companies in Asia L2: Close collab. Peking University, Qilu University of Technology L3: Collaboration with other large actors L4: not specific, mentions multi-disciplinary and digital enablers L5: No info.</p>
<p>Ebecryl 6000</p>	<p>M1: 23 research and technology support centers globally, Recent main research centre for sustainable coatings in Austria</p>	<p>M1: Not specific, mentions 5 JV with world-class companies in Asia</p>
<p>TMP(EO)TA</p>	<p>N1: >200 patents in 2023 (90% related to sustainable development), 1800 researchers in 17 R&D centres. N2: 23 research and technology support centers globally, Recent main research centre for sustainable coatings in Austria N3: Innovation at the core of strategy, own research department Around 1000 new patents in 2023 €2.1 bn expenses for R&D in 2023 4,029 employees in R&D 2023 N4: No info. N5: €443 million in R&D in 2023 227 new patents in 2023 Own strategic innovation unit and business incubator.</p>	<p>N1: Not specified. N2: Not specific, mentions 5 JV with world-class companies in Asia N3: World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) Nova-Institute’s Renewable Carbon Initiative Collaboration with around 200 research partners (universities, institutes, alliances) N4: No info. N5: Partnerships with multiple universities and research institutions across Europe, Asia, North America</p>

	<p>N6: Science and Lab unit invested tens of millions EUR on R&D facilities in 2023, targeting biotech and pharmaceuticals</p> <p>EUR 2.4 billion for R&D in 2023</p>	<p>N6: not specific on this, but mentions multi-disciplinary and focus on digital enablers</p>
DPGDA	<p>P1: Website presents R&D and boasts of patents in 2023, but is not specific on numbers</p> <p>P2: €374 million R&D expenses 2023, per now 52% aligned R&D portfolio to SDGs, 80% by 2025</p> <p>P3: R&D focus on eco-friendly substances and green energy materials to reduce GHG emissions and volatile organic compounds (VOCs); develop decomposable and recyclable products</p> <p>P4: No specific info, except R&D is important, e.g., with customers</p> <p>P5: No specific info.</p> <p>P6: No specific info.</p>	<p>P1: Collaboration with other large actors</p> <p>P2: "Open innovation" as key to success</p> <p>P3: Own R&D Division, but also external collaboration</p> <p>P4: No specific info.</p> <p>P5: No specific info.</p> <p>P6: No specific info.</p>

Annex B: CoCs and their coverage

Component	Availability of CoC and/or SCoC	Coverage
Novel biobased binder (from xylose)	A1: no/no	A1: no information
Novel biobased binder (from cellobiose)	B1: no/no	B1: no information
GPTA	C1: yes/yes C2: no/no C3: yes/yes C4: yes*/no C5: yes/no* C6: no/no C7: no/no	C1: CoC: Elaborated definition of fair competition, own and suppliers' responsibilities, grievance mechanisms; SCoC: expectation of compliance with anti-trust regulations. Using sustainability assessments for their suppliers (TfS) – over 60% relevant suppliers in 2023 C2: no CoC or SCoC available C3: commits to compliance with competition laws, expects similar commitments from its suppliers through its SCoC C4: CoC* (Code of Ethics included in the annual report) and emphasises anti-corruption as an important element of their corporate governance C5: emphasises compliance with relevant laws and regulations in all jurisdictions of their operations (specific focus on anti-corruption) C6: no CoC or SCoC available C7: no information
Ebecryl 4690	D1: yes/yes	D1: CoC: clauses on compliance with national and international regulatory frameworks on anti-corruption, competition etc. SCoC: suppliers are expected to comply with laws, including anti-corruption and fair competition laws
Laromer PO77F	E1: yes/yes	E1: CoC: describes their compliance with fair competition related laws and regulatory frameworks, their own practices (e.g., relations with suppliers); SCoC: expectations regarding

		suppliers’ compliance and reservation of the right to conduct audits or assessments to ensure this compliance, as well as the right to withdraw from the partnership in case of non-compliance or violations)
Tego Airex 990	F1: yes/yes	F1: CoC: states its compliance with relevant anti-trust and competition laws, tax and anti money-laundering regulations wherever applicable, whistleblower mechanisms established to report breaches of the CoC; SCoC: requires suppliers’ compliance with similar principles, compliance with laws, establishment of grievance mechanisms, appropriate mitigation of identified risks and breaches, immediate notification of their client in case of breaches and violations, promotion of similar principles throughout their supply bases. Reservation of the right to conduct audits or assessments to ensure this compliance, as well as the right to suspend or withdraw from the partnership in case of non-compliance or violations.
Jetfine 2*	G1: yes/yes	G1: CoC: compliance with relevant laws and regulations; SCoc: expect suppliers to comply with relevant competition laws and regulations (e.g., antitrust regulations), promote similar principles throughout their value chains and report violations using the whistleblower mechanisms.
Acematt OK412	H1: yes/yes	H1: CoC: states its compliance with relevant anti-trust and competition laws, tax and anti-money-laundering regulations wherever applicable, whistleblower mechanisms established to report breached of the CoC; SCoC: requires suppliers’ compliance with similar principles , compliance with local and international laws, establishment of grievance mechanisms, appropriate mitigation of identified risks and breaches, immediate notification of their client in case of breaches and violations, promotion of similar principles throughout their supply bases. Reservation of the right to conduct audits or assessments to ensure this compliance, as well as the right to suspend or withdraw from the partnership in case of non-compliance or violations.

<p>HF2086</p>	<p>J1: yes/yes J2: yes/yes J3: yes/yes J4: no/no J5: yes/yes</p>	<p>J1: Compliance with relevant laws and regulations (both); encourage suppliers to adopt similar approach throughout their value chains; J2: address both own and suppliers’ obligation to comply with respective laws and regulations; suppliers’ inability to comply can result in termination of partnerships and agreements, reserve a right to conduct audits of the suppliers’ compliance with the Supplier Code of Conduct J3: commit to the principles of fair competition and declare their compliance with respective laws and regulations, encourage their suppliers to support their same principles J4: no information J5: CoC: dedication to the principles of fair competition and compliance with the respective laws and regulations, e.g., antitrust, anti-corruption etc; compliance is expected from the suppliers, conducts audits and potential termination in case of suppliers’ non-compliance. Whistleblowing mechanisms are in place.</p>
<p>Tego RAD 2500</p>	<p>K1: yes/yes</p>	<p>K1: CoC: compliance with relevant anti-trust and competition laws, tax and anti money-laundering regulations wherever applicable, whistleblower mechanisms established to report breached of the CoC; SCoC: requires suppliers to comply with similar principles local and international laws, promotes establishment of grievance mechanisms, appropriate mitigation of identified risks and breaches, expects immediate notification of their client in case of breaches and violations, promotion of similar principles throughout their supply bases. Reservation of the right to conduct audits or assessments and the right to suspend or withdraw from the partnership in case of non-compliance or violations.</p>
<p>DPHA</p>	<p>L1: yes/yes L2: no/no L3: yes/yes L4: yes/yes L5: no/no</p>	<p>L1: CoC: clauses on compliance with national and international regulatory frameworks on anti-corruption, competition etc. SCoC: suppliers are expected to comply with laws, including anti-corruption and fair competition laws L3: commits to compliance with competition laws, expects similar commitments from its suppliers</p>

		<p>L4: CoC: Elaborated definition of fair competition, description of own and suppliers’ responsibilities, grievance mechanisms in place; SCoC: expectation of compliance with anti-trust regulations.</p> <p>Using sustainability assessments for their suppliers (TfS) – over 60% relevant suppliers in 2023</p> <p>L5: no information</p>
Ebecryl 6000	M1: yes/yes	<p>M1: CoC: clauses on compliance with national and international regulatory frameworks on anti-corruption, competition etc. SCoC: suppliers are expected to comply with laws, including anti-corruption and fair competition laws</p>
TMP(EO)TA	<p>N1: yes/yes</p> <p>N2: yes/yes</p> <p>N3: yes/yes</p> <p>N4: no/no</p> <p>N5: yes/yes</p> <p>N6: yes/yes</p>	<p>N1: CoC: declares its dedication to the principles of fair competition and compliance with the respective laws and regulations, e.g., antitrust, anti-corruption etc; compliance is expected from the suppliers Whistleblowing mechanisms are in place. Sanctions are in place: audits and potential termination in case of non-compliance</p> <p>N2: CoC: clauses on compliance with national and international regulatory frameworks on anti-corruption, competition etc. SCoC: suppliers are expected to comply with laws, including anti-corruption and fair competition laws</p> <p>N3: CoC: describes their compliance with fair competition related laws and regulatory frameworks, their own practices (e.g., relations with suppliers); SCoC: expectations regarding suppliers’ compliance and reservation of the right to conduct audits or assessments to ensure this compliance, as well as the right to withdraw from the partnership in case of non-compliance or violations</p> <p>N4: No specific info</p> <p>N5: CoC: states its compliance with relevant anti-trust and competition laws, tax and anti money-laundering regulations wherever applicable, whistleblower mechanisms established to report breaches of the CoC; SCoC: compliance with similar principles as the actor themselves, compliance with local and</p>

		<p>international laws, establishment of grievance mechanisms, appropriate mitigation of identified risks and breaches, immediate notification of their client in case of breaches and violations, promotion of similar principles throughout their supply bases. Reservation of the right to conduct audits or assessments to ensure this compliance, as well as the right to suspend or withdraw from the partnership in case of non-compliance or violations.</p> <p>N6: CoC: Elaborated definition of fair competition, description of own and suppliers’ responsibilities, grievance mechanisms in place, uses sustainability assessments for their suppliers (TfS); SCoC: expectation of compliance with anti-trust regulations,</p>
DPGDA	<p>P1: yes/yes P2: yes/yes P3: no/no P4: no/no P5: no/no P6: no/no</p>	<p>P1: commits to compliance with competition laws, expects similar commitments from its suppliers</p> <p>P2: CoC: under revision, emphasises compliance in general and refers to the SCoC; SCoC: Suppliers are expected to comply with relevant laws and conduct their business in line with fair competition.</p> <p>P3: No specific info P4: No specific info P5: No specific info P6: No specific info</p>

Annex C: Human rights efforts

Component	Stated efforts to enhance human rights (non-exhaustive list)
Novel biobased binder (from xylose)	A1: No information.
Novel biobased binder (from cellobiose)	B1: No information.
GPTA	<p>C1: address human rights aspects in the Code of Conduct, Human Rights Charter, and Human Rights Policy Statement anchored in universal documents and respective national laws, report in addition to the requirements of some national laws. Participate in UN Global Compact (includes human rights dimension), expect their external partners to respect the same principles (stated in Supplier Code of Conduct). Established grievance mechanism (encourage suppliers to have grievance mechanisms in place as well), provide courses for employees etc.</p> <p>C2: no information.</p> <p>C3: Labour and Human Rights Policy and CSR Statement in place – commitment to respect human rights across its operations globally (anchored in UN Global Compact Principles); CoC: contains detailed definitions of actions that constitute a breach of human and labour rights, reporting routines, respect to human rights also promoted in their Supplier Code of Conduct</p> <p>C4: includes human rights aspect in their corporate governance policy and reporting, refer to ILO Guidelines and own Code of Ethics (included in annual report, not found separately), connect it to specific SDGs and respective targets</p> <p>C5: anchors its Modern Slavery Policy in United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the United Nations Conventions on the Rights of the Child and International Labour Organisation Core Labour Standards, emphasis on expectations to their suppliers to promote similar principles through their commitment to Work Practices Code of Conduct</p> <p>C6: no information</p> <p>C7: no information</p>

Ebecryl 4690	D1: address human rights aspects through their Code of Conduct, Supplier Code of Conduct, reflecting their Labour and Human Rights Policy. Participate in UN Global Compact reporting on ESG. Have established grievance mechanisms globally.
Laromer PO77F	E1: issued Policy Statement on Human Rights, through their Code of Conduct commit to internationally agreed-upon standards (e.g., the United Nations' Universal Declaration on Human Rights, the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, the OECD Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises and the Tripartite Declaration of Principles Concerning Multinational Enterprises and Social Policy (MNE Declaration) of ILO). Expect their suppliers to respect and protect human rights, offer to help suppliers meeting their responsibilities in this regard.
Tego Airex 990	F1: Apply international standards (e.g., ILO international labour standards), include human rights aspect in their Global Social Policy and Code of Conduct, in accordance with their Code of Conduct for Suppliers expect suppliers to reject and actively combat possible violations, as well as address the risks related to human rights in their respective value chains, comply with respective national laws (e.g., Due Diligence Act in Germany), have established whistleblower system, conduct human rights risk assessments, report within various sustainability related initiatives (e.g., UN Global Compact).
Jetfine 2*	G1: commit to The UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, ILO Fundamental Conventions, emphasise respect to human rights in their Code of Conduct, in accordance with their Supplier Code of Conduct, suppliers are expected to promote similar principles throughout their value chains and report violations using the whistleblower mechanisms.
Acematt OK412	H1: Apply international standards (e.g., ILO international labour standards), include human rights aspect in their Global Social Policy and Code of Conduct, in accordance with their Code of Conduct for Suppliers expect suppliers to reject and actively combat possible violations, as well as address the risks related to human rights in their respective value chains, comply with respective national laws (e.g., Due Diligence Act in Germany), have established whistleblower system, conduct human rights risk assessments, report within various sustainability related initiatives (e.g., UN Global Compact).
HF2086	J1: state an overall commitment to respect international principles on human rights, expectation to suppliers to respect human rights, avoid any form for child

	<p>labour or forced labour in their Supplier Code of Conduct, encourage suppliers to adopt similar approach throughout their respective value chains.</p> <p>J2: Commit to United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, Ten Principles of the United Nations Global Compact, the International Labor Organization’s Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work, and all applicable laws of the jurisdictions where they operate. Address both own and suppliers’ obligation to comply with respective laws and regulations; suppliers’ inability to comply can result in termination of partnerships and agreements, reserve a right to conduct audits of the suppliers’ compliance with the Supplier Code of Conduct. Human rights violations (as well as potential violations of the commitments in this regard) can be reported by anyone through a whistleblow mechanism</p> <p>J3: CoC: commit to respecting human rights, list relevant laws and regulations with which they comply; emphasise their collaboration with suppliers who share their value, including respect for human rights; reporting channels for violations of the Code of Conduct available</p> <p>J4: no information</p> <p>J5: CoC: anchors its values on human rights in Universal declaration of human rights, the principles of the ILO, the Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), and follows the principles of the United Nations Global Compact, has a whistleblowing system in place. Through their Supplier Code of Conduct requires the suppliers to comply with international standards and relevant national laws and regulations on human and labour rights; reserve the right to conduct audits or assessments to ensure this compliance and the right to withdraw from the partnership in case of non-compliance or violations.</p>
<p>Tego RAD 2500</p>	<p>K1: Apply international standards (e.g., ILO international labour standards), include human rights aspect in their Global Social Policy and Code of Conduct, in accordance with their Code of Conduct for Suppliers expect suppliers to reject and actively combat possible violations, as well as address the risks related to human rights in their respective value chains, comply with respective national laws (e.g., Due Diligence Act in Germany), have established whistleblower system, conduct human rights risk assessments, report within various sustainability related initiatives (e.g., UN Global Compact)</p>
<p>DPHA</p>	<p>L1: address human rights aspects through their Code of Conduct, Supplier Code of Conduct, reflecting their Labour and Human Rights Policy. Participate in UN</p>

	<p>Global Compact reporting on ESG. Have established grievance mechanisms globally.</p> <p>L2: no information.</p> <p>L3: Labour and Human Rights Policy and CSR Statement in place with articulated commitment to respect human rights across its operations globally (anchored in UN Global Compact Principles); CoC: contains detailed definitions of actions that constitute a breach of human and labour rights, reporting routines, respect to human rights is also promoted in their Supplier Code of Conduct</p> <p>L4: address human rights aspects in the Code of Conduct, Human Rights Charter, and Human Rights Policy Statement anchored in universal documents and respective national laws, report in addition to the requirements of some national laws. Participate in UN Global Compact (includes human rights dimension), expect their external partners to respect the same principles (stated in Supplier Code of Conduct). Established grievance mechanism (encourage suppliers to have grievance mechanisms in place as well), provide courses for employees etc.</p> <p>L5: no information</p>
<p>Ebecryl 6000</p>	<p>M1: address human rights aspects through their Code of Conduct, Supplier Code of Conduct, reflecting their Labour and Human Rights Policy. Participate in UN Global Compact reporting on ESG. Have established grievance mechanisms globally.</p>
<p>TMP(EO)TA</p>	<p>N1: CoC: commits to respect Universal declaration of human rights, the principles of the International Labour Organisation; refers to the Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and the principles of the United Nations Global Compact, has a whistleblowing system in place. Through their Supplier Code of Conduct requires the suppliers to comply with international standards and relevant national laws and regulations on human and labour rights; reserve the right to conduct audits or assessments to ensure this compliance, as well as the right to suspend or withdraw from the partnership in case of non-compliance or violations.</p> <p>N2: address human rights aspects through their Code of Conduct, Supplier Code of Conduct, reflecting their Labour and Human Rights Policy. Participate in UN Global Compact reporting on ESG. Have established grievance mechanisms globally.</p> <p>N3: issued Policy Statement on Human Rights, through their Code of Conduct</p>

	<p>commit to internationally agreed-upon standards, such as the United Nations’ Universal Declaration on Human Rights, the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, the OECD Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises and the Tripartite Declaration of Principles Concerning Multinational Enterprises and Social Policy (MNE Declaration) of the International Labor Organization (ILO). Expect their suppliers to respect and protect human rights, offer to help suppliers meeting their responsibilities in this regard</p> <p>N4: no information</p> <p>N5: Apply international standards (e.g., ILO international labour standards), include human rights aspect in their Global Social Policy and Code of Conduct, in accordance with their Code of Conduct for Suppliers expect suppliers to reject and actively combat possible violations, as well as address the risks related to human rights in their respective value chains, comply with respective national laws (e.g., Due Diligence Act in Germany), have established whistleblower system, conduct human rights risk assessments, report within various sustainability related initiatives (e.g., UN Global Compact).</p> <p>N6: address human rights aspects in the Code of Conduct, Human Rights Charter, and Human Rights Policy Statement anchored in universal documents and respective national laws, report in addition to the requirements of some national laws. Participate in UN Global Compact (includes human rights dimension), expect their external partners to respect the same principles (stated in Supplier Code of Conduct). Established grievance mechanism (encourage suppliers to have grievance mechanisms in place as well), provide courses for employees etc.</p>
<p>DPGDA</p>	<p>P1: established Labour and Human Rights Policy and CSR Statement in place – commitment to respect human rights across its operations globally (anchored in UN Global Compact Principles); CoC: contains detailed definitions of actions that constitute a breach of human and labour rights, reporting routines, respect to human rights also promoted in their Supplier Code of Conduct</p> <p>P2: Commits to UN Global Compact’s core principles, Universal Declaration of Human Rights, P2 Specific Position on Human Rights (policy document)</p> <p>P3: Commits to implement their Human Rights Policy, The International Human Rights Code, ILOs standards</p> <p>P4: No specific info</p> <p>P5: No specific info (low transparency score in third party ranking)</p>

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Report on social acceptance and impacts study

	P6: No specific info
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Annex D: Diversity and inclusion: Gender

Component	Women in proportion to total workforce	Proportion of women in management	Stated measures to improve gender balance
Novel biobased binder (from xylose)	A1: No info.	A1: -	A1: no info.
Novel biobased binder (from cellobiose)	B1: No info.	B1: No info.	B1: No info.
GPTA	C1: 35% C2: no info. C3: not specified. C4: No info. C5: 37% C6: No info.	C1: 39% C2: no info. C3: 25% in first tier, 30% if second tier included C4: No info. C5: No info. C6: No info.	C1: 2023, added two new focus SDGs, gender equality, diversity, equal opportunities, and inclusion C2: no info. C3: target 50% in first tier by 2030. C4: No info. C5: No info. C6: no info. (Pictures on the web suggest high share of women in management and generally)
Ebecryl 4690	D1: 25%	D1: 27%	D1: Only 11% in manufacturing, but has special programs and target to increase the share of females. Aim for 30% in manag. By 2030
Laromer PO77F	E1: 26.7%	E1: 28.4%	E1: Wants 30% in manag. By 2030.
Tego Airex 990	F1: 47.1%	F1: 34.4%	F1: Supports social impetus and takes part in alliances to encourage young women to enter STEM professions. "Grow beyond yourself" initiative in Asia-Pacific targets the same professions

Jetfine 2*	G1: 24.4%	G1: 27%	G1: 2021 Signature of the Women’s Empowerment Principles (UN WEPs)
Acematt OK412	H1: 47.1%	H1: 34.4%	H1: Supports social impetus and takes part in alliances to encourage young women to enter STEM professions. “Grow beyond yourself” initiative in Asia-Pacific targets the same professions
HF2086	J1: 24% J2: 29.5% J3: 26.8% J4: 15% J5: 26,8%	J1: 26.3% J2: 21.40% (executives) J3: 26.1% J4: No info. J5: 29%	J1: Aims for 50% women in management in 10 years J2: Women’s employee network, Women’s Career Advancement Program J3: Aim of 30% female managers J4: No info. J5: Target 30% by 2030.
Tego RAD 2500	K1: 47.1%	K1: 34.4%	K1: Supports social impetus and takes part in alliances to encourage young women to enter STEM professions. “Grow beyond yourself” initiative in Asia-Pacific targets the same professions
DPHA	L1: 25% L2: No info. L3: No info. L4: 35% L5: No info.	L1: 27% L2: no info. L3: 25% in first tier, 30% if second tier L4: 39% L5: No info.	L1: Only 11% in manufacturing, but has special programs and target to increase the share of females. Aim for 30% in manag. By 2030 L2: no info. L3: target 50% in first tier by 2030. L4: 2023, added two new focus SDGs, gender equality, diversity, equal opportunities, and inclusion L5: No info.
Ebecryl 6000	M1: 25%	M1: 27%	M1: Only 11% in manufacturing, but has special programs and target to increase the share of females. Aim for 30% in manag. By 2030
TMP(EO)TA	N1: 26.8% N2: 25% N3: 26.7% N4: No info. N5: 47.1%	N1: 29% N2: 27% N3: 28.4% N4: No info N5: 34.4%	N1: target 30% women executives by 2030 N2: Only 11% in manufacturing, but has special programs and target to increase the share of females. Aim for 30% in manag. By 2030 N3: Wants 30% in manag. By 2030.

			<p>N4: no info.</p> <p>N5: Supports social impetus and takes part in alliances to encourage young women to enter STEM professions. "Grow beyond yourself" initiative in Asia-Pacific targets the same professions</p>
DPGDA	<p>P1: Not specified</p> <p>P2: 23.2%</p> <p>P3: 17% (Numbers by region)</p> <p>P4: No info.</p> <p>P5: No info.</p> <p>P6: No info.</p>	<p>P1: 25% in first tier, 30% if second tier</p> <p>P2: Level 1, 0%, Level 2, 36.8%</p> <p>P3: 4%</p> <p>P4: No info.</p> <p>P5: No info.</p> <p>P6: No info.</p>	<p>P1: target 50% in first tier by 2030. Ambition to have 50% females in first and second tier management by 2030 (IGM Resins)</p> <p>P2: Targets to increase number of women at all levels</p> <p>P3: Focus on pay and maternity leave, aim at a system of hiring, promotion, performance appraisal, and salaries is not affected by gender.</p> <p>P4: No info.</p> <p>P5: No info.</p> <p>P6: No info.</p>

Annex E: Health and safety

Component	Hazards	Injury rates
Novel biobased binder (from xylose)	A1: No info.*	A1: No info.
Novel biobased binder (from cellobiose)	B1: No info.**	B2: No info.
GPTA	May cause an allergic skin reaction Causes serious eye irritation	C1: LTIR 1.3. EHS incident rate: 2.4 C2: No info. C3: RIR: 1.2 C4: LTIR: 1.2 C5: Lost time injury frequency rate: 12.8 C6: No info. C7: No info.
Ebecryl 4690	Causes skin irritation. Causes serious eye irritation May cause an allergic skin reaction.	D1: RIR 0.48.
Laromer PO77F	Causes serious eye irritation. May cause an allergic skin reaction. Suspected of damaging fertility. Suspected of damaging the unborn child.	E1: RIR 0.82.
Tego Airex 990	May be fatal if swallowed and enters airways. Causes skin irritation. May cause drowsiness or dizziness. Suspected of damaging the unborn child.	F1: RIR 0.43.

	<p>May cause damage to organs through prolonged or repeated exposure.</p> <p>Highly flammable.</p>	
Jetfine 2*	<p>May irritate the skin</p> <p>Can irritate the nose, throat, and lungs</p> <p>Not classified with respect to cancer</p> <p>Needs further testing with respect to reproductive harm</p>	G1: TRIR 2.19
Acematt OK412	<p>No SARA Hazards (however, dust may cause some irritation, and it could have a drying effect on the skin</p>	H1: RIR 0.43.
HF2086	<p>Fatal if swallowed.</p> <p>Fatal in contact with skin.</p> <p>Causes severe skin burns and eye damage.</p> <p>Causes serious eye damage.</p> <p>Fatal if inhaled.</p>	<p>J1: RIR 0.27.</p> <p>J2: RIR 0.29</p> <p>J3: RIR 0.6</p> <p>J4: No info.</p> <p>J5: TRIR 0.9.</p>
Tego RAD 2500	<p>May cause an allergic skin reaction</p>	K1: 0.43
DPHA	<p>Causes skin irritation.</p> <p>May cause an allergic skin reaction</p>	<p>L1: RIR 0.48</p> <p>L2: No info.</p> <p>L3: RIR 1.2</p> <p>L4: Lost time injury rate: 1.3. EHS incident rate: 2.4</p> <p>L5: No info.</p>
Ebecryl 6000	<p>May cause an allergic skin reaction</p>	M1: RIR 0.48
TMP(EO)TA	<p>Low/no flammability</p> <p>Low/zero VOC</p>	<p>N1: TRIR 0.9</p> <p>N2: RIR 0.48.</p> <p>N3: RIR 0.82</p> <p>N4: No info.</p>

		N5: RIR 0.43.
DPGDA	<p>Causes skin irritation</p> <p>May cause an allergic skin reaction</p> <p>Causes serious eye damage</p> <p>May be harmful if swallowed</p>	<p>P1: RIR: 1.2</p> <p>P2: RIR 0.31</p> <p>P3: TRIR 0.13 (2021)</p> <p>P4: No info.</p> <p>P5: No info.</p> <p>P6: No info.</p>

*For xylose more broadly, a low hazard for usual industrial handling is reported. May cause eye, skin, and respiratory tract irritation.³⁶

**For cellobiose more broadly, there are no known harmful effects, when used and handled according to specifications, and the substance is not subject to e.g., ECHA classification.³⁷

³⁶ <https://westliberty.edu/health-and-safety/files/2012/08/D-plus-or-minus-Xylose.pdf>

³⁷ <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Cellobiose#section=Hazard-Classes-and-Categories>

Annex F: Community welfare and engagement

Component	Community welfare, funding support	Community engagement
Novel biobased binder (from xylose)	A1: No.	A1: No.
Novel biobased binder (from cellobiose)	B1: No.	B1: No
GPTA	<p>C1: supporting WASH related initiatives, cultural and educational activities, open innovation sharing</p> <p>C2: None reported.</p> <p>C3: Impact day (employees giving back to community)</p> <p>C4: Foundation providing support for schooling (1900 students, 2021)</p> <p>C5: "open to aligning with charity or community outreach programs where possible"</p> <p>C6: No info available online.</p> <p>C7: No</p>	<p>C1: Community engagement spending 47.2 million EUR in 2023</p> <p>C2: None reported.</p> <p>C3: None specified.</p> <p>C4: Community engagement highlighted, but not specified</p> <p>C5: Not specified</p> <p>C6: No info available online.</p> <p>C7: no.</p>
Ebecryl 4690	<p>D1: Not specific on activities. But stated intent to increasing the number of products produced locally – particularly in APAC.</p>	<p>D1: Listing various specific, smaller outreach activities.</p>
Laromer PO77F	<p>E1: Intrapreneurship program, Starting Ventures, targeting low-income areas. In addition, support for health and education.</p>	<p>E1: €37 million for societal engagement activities in 2023 (multiple business areas).</p>

Tego Airex 990	F1: Donations for education, social projects (25%), culture, sports, other. Supports initiatives to improve opportunities for girls in developing countries	F1: Donated 3.9 million EUR in 2023. Stakeholder engagement emphasized, for community/residents main topic 2023 was green energy.
Jetfine 2*	G1: education, improving infrastructure and livelihoods in SA mining area. Creating development partnerships with customers or startups through open innovation challenges and technical days	G1: Not spending but stakeholder mapping as metrics. 35 new initiatives in 2023.
Acematt OK412	H1: Donations for education, social projects (25%), culture, sports, other. Supports initiatives to improve opportunities for girls in developing countries	H1: Donated 3.9 million EUR in 2023. Stakeholder engagement emphasized, for community/residents main topic 2023 was green energy.
HF2086	<p>J1: Wants to have community impact in terms of support for education and other.</p> <p>J2: Sponsoring STEM education, humanitarian relief, inclusion and diversity</p> <p>J3: Supports charity in the social environment of its locations, measuring impact and number of beneficiaries.</p> <p>J4: Strong emphasis on supporting public welfare (5 major funds)</p> <p>J5: Donations for education, professional integration, diversity, environmental protection and health</p>	<p>J1: Not specific in terms of spending or targets.</p> <p>J2: Spending and specific measures to promote community engagement are not mentioned</p> <p>J3: At larger sites, participation in institutionalized dialogues, such as community advisory boards. There are also contact points in the communities and established grievance procedures.</p> <p>J4: Substantial spending on this, multiple figures on website</p> <p>J5: "Common Ground" approach, to build relationships between the Company, its industrial sites and their</p>

		ecosystem. "ChemArt Green Innovation Classes"
Tego RAD 2500	K1: Donations for education, social projects (25%), culture, sports, other. Supports initiatives to improve opportunities for girls in developing countries	K1: Donated 3.9 million EUR in 2023. Stakeholder engagement emphasized, for community/residents main topic 2023 was green energy.
DPHA	L1: Not specific. L2: None reported. L3: Impact day (employees giving back to community) L4: supporting WASH related initiatives, cultural and educational activities, open innovation sharing. L5: No information.	L1: Listing various specific, smaller outreach activities. L2: None reported. L3: None specified. L4: Community engagement spending 47.2 million EUR in 2023 L5: No information.
Ebecryl 6000	M1: Not specific. But stated intent to increasing the number of products produced locally – particularly in APAC.	M1: Listing various specific, smaller outreach activities.
TMP(EO)TA	N1: Donations for education, professional integration, diversity, environmental protection and health N2: Not specific. N3: Intrapreneurship program, Starting Ventures, targeting low-income areas. In addition, support for health and education. N4: No info available online. N5: Donations for education, social projects (25%), culture, sports, other. Supports initiatives to improve	N1: "Common Ground" approach, to build relationships between the Company, its industrial sites and their ecosystem. "ChemArt Green Innovation Classes" N2: D1: Listing various specific, smaller outreach activities. N3; €37 million for societal engagement activities in 2023 (multiple business areas). N4: No info available online. N5; Donated 3.9 million EUR in 2023. Stakeholder engagement emphasized, for community/residents main topic 2023 was green energy.

	<p>opportunities for girls in developing countries</p> <p>N6: supporting WASH related initiatives, cultural and educational activities, open innovation sharing</p>	<p>N6: Community engagement spending 47.2 million EUR in 2023</p>
<p>DPGDA</p>	<p>P1: Impact day (employees giving back to community)</p> <p>P2: "Inclusive Business" comprises collaboration with development agencies and 'green' initiatives in India, Africa and Asia,</p> <p>P3: Support for various community welfare activities, social, environmental and cultural</p> <p>P4: No information online.</p> <p>P5: No information online.</p> <p>P6: No information online.</p>	<p>P1: None specified.</p> <p>P2: "Inclusive Business" model, focusing on unmet needs of communities in underserved markets (6.7 mill beneficiaries, 2023).</p> <p>P3: the noted activities not accompanied by specific targets or stated expenditure</p> <p>P4: No information online.</p> <p>P5: No information online.</p> <p>P6: No information online.</p>

Annex G: Reporting and product information

Component	Online annual/financial reports	Online sustainability policy, reporting	Open product info online
Novel bio. binder (from xylose)	A1: no	A1: no	A1: No
Novel bio. binder (from cellobiose)	B1: no	B1: no	B1: EPD
GPTA	C1: yes. C2: yes. C3: no, not any detailed financial statements. C4: yes. C5: yes. C6: no. C7: no.	C1: yes, including strategy and detailed GRI disclosures. C2: no C3: Corporate Sustainability Report, with key metrics and success stories. C4: yes, in annual report. Key metrics and successes. C5: In annual report. Key metrics. C6: no C7: no.	C1: SDS online C2: Description online, nothing on hazards. C3: Must register to get TDS. C4: Specification online, with hazards. C5: Must register to get TDS and SDS. C6: Must send enquiry.C7: No, but some essentials, incl. hazards, mentioned on webpage.
Ebecryl 4690	D1: Yes.	D1: yes, with GRI disclosures.	D1: TDS downloadable. SDS on request.
Laromer PO77F	E1: Yes.	E1: Yes. With SFDR Index for 2023 and full CSRD reporting from 2024	E1: SDS can be downloaded
Tego Airex 990	F1: Yes.	F1: Yes, with GRI disclosures.	F1: TDS and SDS available online
Jetfine 2*	G1: Yes.	G1: Reached its limit for free views.	G1: SDS not directly available online

Acematt OK412	H1: Yes.	H1: Yes	H1: TDS and brochure openly available. SDS can be found, but not directly from the corporate website.
HF2086	J1: Yes. J2: Yes, very detailed. J3: Yes. J4: Yes. J5: Yes.	J1: Yes, integrated including GRI Index. J2: Yes, with disclosures according to SASB framework J3: Yes, various docs. ESG fact sheet most concrete. J4: no. J5: Yes. Key metrics and successes.	J1: TDS and SDS not available online J2: TDS and SDS not available online J3: TDS and SDS not available. J4: TDS and SDS not available. J5: TDS and SDS not available online
Tego RAD 2500	K1: Yes.	K1: Yes, with GRI disclosures.	TDS and SDS available online
DPHA	L1: Yes. L2: No. L3: No. L4: Yes. L5: No.	L1: Yes, with GRI disclosures. L2: No. L3: CSR Report, with key metrics and success stories. L4: yes, including strategy and detailed GRI disclosures. L5: No.	L1: Downloadable TDS, SDS on request L2: No, must contact them. L3: Downloadable TDS, SDS no. L4: TDS and SDS both available. L5: No.
Ebecryl 6000	M1: Yes.	M1: Yes, with GRI disclosures.	M1: Downloadable TDS, SDS on request
TMP(EO)TA	N1: Yes. N2: Yes. N3: Yes.	N1: Yes. Key metrics and successes. N2: Yes, with GRI disclosures.	N1: Requires customer code. N2: Downloadable TDS, SDS on request N3: Yes, both TDS and SDS

	<p>N4: No. N5: Yes. N6: yes.</p>	<p>N3: Yes. With SFDR Index for 2023 and full CSRD reporting from 2024 N4: No. N5: Yes, with GRI disclosures. N6: yes, including strategy and detailed GRI disclosures.</p>	<p>N4: No, must send enquiry. N5: TDS and SDS available online. N6: Yes, TDS and SDS</p>
DPGDA	<p>P1: Not in detail. P2: Yes. P3: Yes, not very accessible. P4: No. P5: Latest 2020/2021 P6: No.</p>	<p>P1: Corporate Sustainability Report, with key metrics and success stories. P2: Not easy to find, but much info available (e.g., sustainability policy GRI disclosures). P3: Yes, but from 2021 (laid out with GRI indicators) P4: No. P5: No. P6: No.</p>	<p>P1: TDS downloadable, SDS must register P2: TDS available, SDS must be searched for in database P3: No (for purchase through other websites) P4: Technical description, but not TDS or SDS P5: No, must contact them. P6: No, must contact.</p>